

52. Sristidhar Dutta, *op.cit.*, p. 13. Also see E.A. Gait, *A History of Assam*, second edition. Calcutta, 1926, p. 59.

Since the days of the Māyāmarīā rebellion consistent efforts have been made to blacken the character of the Māyāmarīā disciples and their Gurus including Gopāladeva and Aniruddhadeva; See 'Vaiṣṇavism in Kāmarūpa' by Sarat Chandra Goswami in the *Journal of the Assam Research Society*, Vol. I, No 2. The *Ādi-Carita* ascribed to Mādhavadeva (spurious) created much ill feeling among the Vaiṣṇavas of Assam and was denounced by them, see Lakṣmīkānta Mahanta of Śrāvaṇī-Sattra, quoted by M. Neog, *op. cit.*, p. 29, fn. Dharmadeva Sarma's *Dharmodaya Nāṭaka* (dramatical work) attempted to blacken the characters of leaders Moāmariā revolt. See M. Neog, *Militancy of the Māyāmarīā Vaiṣṇavas*, p. 71.

But the biography of Aniruddhadeva by Cidānandadeva (1878–1890) published later in 1930 dispelled much of our misgivings about multifaceted personality of Aniruddhadeva.

53. D. Nath 'Social Background of Neo-Vaisnavite Movement in Assam' in *Life and Teachings of ŚrīŚrī Aniruddhadeva*, *op. cit.*, pp. 157ff.
54. For *Maheswar Neog Ruchanāvalī*, vol. I, Guwahati, 1986 as quoted by D. Nath, *op. cit.*, p. 159.
55. Stephen Fuchs, *Rebellious Prophets: A study of Messianic Movements in Indian Religions*, Asia Publishing House, Bombay, 1908, Reprinted 1965, pp. 135-136.
56. S. L. Baruah, *op.cit.*, pp. 183-184.

The Jagjibanpur Plate of Mahendrapāla Comprehensively Re-edited

SURESH CHANDRA BHATTACHARYA

INTRODUCTORY OBSERVATIONS

A copper-plate grant of the hitherto wrongly identified Pāla King Mahendrapāla, discovered on March 13, 1987 in the Jagjibanpur (variants: Jagjivanpur, Jagajibanpur, Jagajjibanpur, etc.) Mouza of the Habibpur Police Station of the Malda District of West Bengal, can easily rank as one of the most important inscriptions of the Pāla period unearthed in recent years. The services of D.C. Sircar, the leading figure in the field of Indian epigraphy for the last several decades being no longer available, other scholars have come forward to make as much sense out of the inscription as possible. This inscription has already been noticed, commented upon, discussed, interpreted, transcribed and translated by a good number of scholars.

The inscription was transcribed by Shyam Chand Mukherji (S. C. Mukherji/Mukherjee=SCM) in the Samskrta Sāhitya Parishat Patrikā (vol. LXVII), but not translated or in any way discussed. Full of errors, this version was followed (with some modifications) by Ashok Chattopadhyay Shastri (=ACS) in his Pāl Abhilekh Sangraha (in Bengali). Besides the text, ACS gave a translation and also made some observations. All this is, however, practically of little use because of the faulty text adopted by him. Kamala Kanta Gupta (=KKG) published his transcript of the text and discussed the contents of the inscription in several of his articles in Bengali periodicals; but he did not offer a full-fledged translation of the inscription. K. V. Ramesh and S. Subramoniya Iyer (=R&I) edited the inscription with transcription (i.e. text), translation and a lengthy discussion about the different aspects of the inscription and their historical bearings in, what was for long, the foremost organ of Indian epigraphic publications, the *Epigraphia Indica*¹ (vol. XLII). In pursuance of this, SCM re-edited the inscription in the *Pratna Samiksha* (vol. 6-8) with text, translation and discussion. Here he gave up many of his earlier readings and followed the footsteps of R&I instead, though not completely. Besides this, SCM published another article on the Jagjibanpur copper-plate inscription of Mahendrapāla in the *Maha-Bodhi Centenary Volume*, Calcutta, where he made some observations on its contents, without bothering to give the text or translation. Many of his assertions here are woefully fanciful and baseless.² Indeed it is difficult to keep

track of the varying positions taken up by him in his different publications for which he did not provide any explanation.

The above-mentioned scholars (except for ACS and SCM in a limited way as pointed out before) worked in isolation without any awareness of or reference to what others had done. This precluded the possibility of effecting any improvement in reading, translation or interpretation by inter-action or exchange or refutation of views, as a result of which backlogs of errors piled up in isolation.

Short of providing the full text and translation, Gouriswar Bhattacharya (=GB), through a number of articles, did much to correct some serious errors of reading and interpretation, particularly by R&I. Amitabha Bhattacharya made some general observations about the inscription in an article or two, but refrained from providing either transcription or translation. B. N. Mukherjee (=BNM)'s limited venture into this inscription, was not of much avail either.

On going through the considerable accumulated literature on the Jagjibanpur copper-plate inscription it appeared to us that there was still enough scope to bring about substantial improvement in all spheres—transcription (i.e. text), translation and interpretation—of this very important document of the Pāla period. The present article is an attempt in this direction. It will be our endeavour to take stock of the works of other scholars alongside our own study and record our position in the light of this exercise. We would be failing in our duty if we do not acknowledge our indebtedness to the cumulative efforts of other scholars for any success in our study of the present inscription.

Rather than following the cut-out format of editing an inscription, we have in the following pages placed an extra burden of responsibility on our own shoulders, as would be obvious to anyone from a perusal of their contents. This has been done to bring the stockpile of the existing errors, differences in reading and interpretation under the scanner and to indicate our own position in a clear-cut manner. Whether the product has been worthy of the effort, can best be judged by the discerning readers.

For the guidance of readers it would be useful to point out at the outset the main features of this article, which include, besides the

1. INTRODUCTORY OBSERVATIONS, the following:-
2. TEXT

3. TRANSLATION
4. DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS
- 5&6. CHECK LISTS (1&2) of Errors/Differences in the Published Readings
7. NOTES (Pertaining to INTRODUCTORY OBSERVATIONS, TEXT, TRANSLATION, DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS)
8. BIBLIOGRAPHY
9. PALAEOGRAPHICAL CHART
10. ILLUSTRATIONS (of the Obverse, Reverse and the Seal at the back).

Details regarding the discovery, early notices etc. have been given by SCM, KKG, GB, R&I etc. scholars, and need not be repeated here. GM. records the dimensions of the copper plate as 52.2×37.1×.05 cm and of the seal as 19×21.8 cm. The accounts of SCM (not self-consistent again) and R&I vary slightly. The copper plate weighs 11 kg 100 gm including the seal (SCM). The edges of the plate are raised into a protective rim except for the area taken up by the seal at the top. The seal portrays the usual Dharmacakra motif represented by a wheel flanked by a couchant deer on either side, being reminiscent of the 'dharma-cakra-pravartana' (turning of the wheel of dharma) by the Buddha at Mṛigadāva in Sarnath, U.P. The seal contains decorative arabesque work and displays the legend 'Śrī-Mahendrapāladevaḥ' in raised letters appearing horizontally below the motif within an inner circle. The seal is firmly fixed onto the plate in the middle on top with nails. The middle of the first three lines on the obverse have been kept blank to accommodate the base of the seal.

Our inscription is in Sanskrit, composed in prose and verse. There are altogether 73 lines of writing, 40 on the obverse and 33 on the reverse. The last line is shorter than the rest and is centred in the middle. The inscription is in a fairly good state of preservation. On the whole the engraver has done his job well, though careless mistakes are not entirely absent.

The palaeography of this inscription is regular for the locality and period of its issue and is in agreement with that of the early Pāla copper plate inscriptions from Bengal and Bihar. Of particular interest is the appearance, simultaneously, of relatively less evolved and more developed forms of some letters (e.g. ṇa, tha, dha, na, etc.). Medial ā has the form of a full-length priṣṭhamātrā, but there are exceptions (cf. jā, ṭā, sphā)

the Palaeographical Chart). Medial u, generally wedge-shaped and placed at the bottom/bottom right, also has other forms (cf. ku, col. 2, ii: nu, tu, stu, ru in the Palaeographical Chart). Medial e has the shape of a wavy śīṛsamātrā; but in ai and au, the first e-mātrā appears as a diminutive curve hanging down from the left end of the letter/head-mark. Halanta (=with virāma) forms of t, n and m call for special attention. Some comments of R&I in respect of the forms of a few letters do not bear the test of scrutiny (e.g. their remarks about initial ā, i and e). R & I failed to take note of the ā-sign in jā (in which the medial ā converges into the tongue of ja), and read the letter sometimes as ja (cf. nijā, nirvyāj=ānati, line 8, etc.). R&I wrongly read ku as initial au, and made fallacious comments on the shape of au. Their observation that 'there are a few instances where the half form of n with the virāma on the left is found represented by an ardhachandra mark with a slightly curved vertical line or virāma below (lines 5,14,16)' is misplaced, for the description applies not to n (as they think), but to m (or rather the Bengali/eastern Indian variety of anusvāra, which, growing out of halanta m, co-existed with the plain dotted type for some time).

The Jagjibanpur copper plate has unveiled the identity of Mahendrapāla as a Pāla king. We now know from recently discovered copper plates that he was succeeded by his younger brother Śūrapāla I and the latter by his own son Gopāla (i.e. Gopāla II), whose existence was unknown before. After Gopāla II, the succession passed on to Vighrapāla I, who represented the collateral branch of the Pālas. The genealogy and chronology of the early Pāla kings is capsuled by us into the following Table in the light of the latest available data:

Table showing
The Genealogy and Chronology of the Early Kings of the Pāla Dynasty

Abbreviations used in this table:

PPM = Parameśvara Paramabhāṭṭāraka Mahārājādhirāja

MKRY = Maximum Known Regnal Year

d = daughter

gd = granddaughter

m = married

In the above Table only actual kings have been assigned serial numbers. The genealogy and chronology of Pāla kings after Nārāyaṇapāla will have to be reconstructed keeping in mind all the factors involved. But this is beyond the scope of our present article.

Before we proceed with the transcription of the text of the inscription, we regret our inability to consult the original copper plate which is now preserved in the District Museum of Malda, West Bengal. In preparing the transcript we have relied on the excellent estampages published in E.I., vol. XLII which have been reproduced along with this article with grateful acknowledgement to the Director General, Archaeological Survey of India, New Delhi, as well as a very good life-size fibre glass cast replica made from the original copper plate, kindly placed at our disposal by Dr. Gautam Sengupta, Director, Directorate of Archaeology & Museums, Govt. of West Bengal. We are indebted to Mr. Subir Sarkar, Administrative officer, American Institute of Indian Studies, Kolkata, and Dr. Sayantani Pal, Lecturer, Department of Ancient Indian History and Culture, Calcutta University, for kindly helping us with copies of some of the articles mentioned in the BIBLIOGRAPHY. We are sorry that it has not been possible for us to consult the works of Mr. Gopal Laha and some others, as these were not available to us but for which these would have been discussed and mentioned in the BIBLIOGRAPHY.

Jagjibanpur Copper-Plate Inscription of Mahendrapāla year 7

TEXT

Metres used:

Śārdūlavikrīḍita-verses 1,4,8,10,13-15,26	Upajāti-9,11,24,28,30
Vasantatilaka-3,6,7,12,16,22,33	Mandākrāntā-34
Mālinī-2,25	Sragdharā-5,7,31,32
Anuṣṭup-17-19,21,23	Hariṇī-29

1. Svasti / Śr(īmān=māni)ta¹-śāsano nija-ba-
2. lair=adhyāsito vī(r)yavān / ary=ānanda² su(sva)bhū-
3. ti-nanditamanā³ dāna-priyaḥ kṣāntimān / bhā-
4. svad-vañ(m)śa-bhavaḥ prajā-hitakaro niḥśeṣa-bhūm=iśvaraḥ Siddhārtho bhuvanāni pātu Sugataḥ pātā ca dharmma-st(th)iteḥ // [1*] Nṛpatir=iha babhūva dhva-
5. sta-doṣ=āndhakāro ravir=iva paṭu⁴-dhāmnān=dhāma-Gopāla-nāmā / agaṇita-guṇa-ratnaṃ yaṃ sam=āsādyā jātā(taṃ) Hari-vasati sukhebhya

The Jagjibanpur Plate of Mahendrapāla Comprehensively Re-edited

6. datta-toy-añjaliḥ Śrīḥ // [2*] Aty-uddhata-dviṣad=anika⁵-jay=ārjjita-śrīḥ śrī-Dharmmapāla-iti tasya suto babhūva / prakṣalitāni kali-sa-
7. utamas=āvilāni yasy=(e)ndun=eva⁶ yaśasā kakubhām=mukhāni // [3*] Durvvārā(n) dviṣato vijitya samare tān=Indra-rāj=ādikān/Sindhūnām=adhipa-
8. m=pramathya⁷ rabhasād=unmī(nmū)lita(m) kṣmābhṛitā / dattā yena mahī Mahodayavati vikrāntibhājo(jā) nijā nirvyāj=ānati⁸-Vāmanāya Balinā Cakrā-
9. yudh=ārthine⁹ // [4*] Reṇu(ū)n=yasy=āṅgaṇebhya hata-ripu-mahiṣi Śva(ā)sa-vātā haranti siñcany(nty)=ētāni¹⁰ mādyat=kari-karata-galad=dāna-toya-pravāhāḥ (/*)
10. rājñām sevāparāṇām=praṇata-nija-śiro-ratna-puṣpa-pratānair=ddaurdarp =ānita-Lakṣmī-kara-kamala-dhṛitaḥ pūjitaḥ pāda-padmaḥ//[5*] Nīter =vvilāsa-bha-
11. vanam=priya-Vikramāyāḥ śrī-Devapāla-iti tat=tanayo babhūva / yaḥ kautukād=iva jagat=padavīn=didrikṣuś=camkramyate sma bhavan=āṅgaṇa-līlay=eva //[6*] Da-
12. ṇḍ=opanīta-kanakair=vvasudh=ādhipānām rājā mahā-samara-nāṭaka-sūtradhāraḥ yo nirmite(ta)¹¹ Sugata-sadma¹² gṛihañ=ca Gauryā¹³ yat=kautukañ=ca tila-
13. kañ=¹⁴ca jagat=traye (=') pi // [7*] Durvvār=āstra-nipāta-bhīṣaṇa-raṇa-(ā)t=saṇnāha-labdh=odayam / sāksikṛitya vibhāvasum raṇa-śirovedī mahā-maṇḍape / kha-
14. ḍg=āvarjjitai(ta)-vairi-vāraṇa-satā¹⁵-kumbhāsṛig=ambhaḥ pluto yo jagrāha karaṃ kṣitīśvara-varo niḥśeṣa-bhu(ū)bhṛid=bhuvām(m)// [8*] Yam yodhayāmāsura-arātayas=te ye-
15. śām riraṃsā sura-sundarībhīḥ / tathā vivasvad=bhramaṇ=āvadhīni ye(ai)ḥ kretum=iṣṭāny=asubhir=yaśān(m)si // [9*] Dharmmasya prasavena yena vipulām=bhūtiñ=ci(m ci)-
16. ram=bibhratā bhrū-līlā-hṛita¹⁶-Kāmarūpa-vibhaven=ārohat=ādym=bhṛi(ū)śam(m)¹⁷ / Durggāyās=ca Himālay=ācala-bhuvāḥ ślāghyañ-(m)karañ=(m)grihnatā samyak-svam¹⁸=pa-
17. rameśvaratvam-aparan=devena sandarśitaṃ(m)// [10*] Sa Cāhamān=ānvaya-vāridh=īndoh sādhvīm sutān-Durlabharāja-nāmnāḥ śrī-Māhatām dharmmaparām narendras=Trai-
18. tīm=iv=oha (ḍha)¹⁹ sa(u)lakṣaṇāṅgīm(m) // [11*] Sā Devak=īva nara-deva-sahasra-vandyam saukaryato vasumatī-bharam=udvahantam(m)/ Lakṣmyāḥ svayam=vara-patim=puruṣo-

19. (tta)mañ=ca devaṃ sut=ottamam=asūta Mahendrapāla(m) // [12*]
Yasy=āśā vijaya-prayāṇe²⁰ rajasām sāndre samutsarppati vyūhe nirbhara-
pu(ū)rit=āmba-
20. (ra)tayā sampādit=orvvi-bhrame²¹ / sprīṣṭe pādatalair=akāṇḍa-patan=
āśaṅkā-camatkārīṇo(nī)-vidyām=utpatan=aika-hetum=ajapan²²=
Vidyādharaṇān(m)=ga-
21. (ṇāḥ) // [13*] Ā-prāleya-girer=vṛiṣ=āṅka-vṛiṣabha-kṣuṇṇ=āgra²³-ratna-
sthalād=ā-Sindhora=Ddaśa-kandhar=āri-viśikha-vyāloḍit=āntarjalāt / ā-
pūrvv=āpa-
22. ra-diñ=mukh=aika-tilakāt²⁴ śaila-dvayād=bhūbhujō(ā) nirvyājam
nipatanti yasya. caraṇe dūr=ānatair²⁵=mmaulibhiḥ // [14*] Khaḍg
=otkhāta-mahebhā-kumbha-vi-
23. galat=kiḷāla-dhārā-jale jāto vairi-vadhū-vilocana-vamad=bāṣp= āmbubhir
=vvarddhitah / santīry = āpi patīn²⁶=apām=pratidiśam yātaḥ sahasrai(r)
=mmukhai-
24. ś=citram=vādhaka-kāruṇ(y)air²⁷=vvilasito yasya pratāp=ānalah / [15*]
Tvaṃ sarvvadā nṛpati-candra-jayaśriy=ārthī svapne(=')pi na praṇayinī
bhavato='ham=ā-
25. sam / ittham=bhiyā kupitay=eva ripūn=bhajantyā vyājaghni²⁸
samara-keli-sukhāni yasya // [16*] Sa khalu Bhāgīrathī-patha-
pravarttamāna-nānā-
26. vidha²⁹-nau-vāṭaka-sampādita-setubandha-nihita-śaila-śikhara-śreṇi-
vibhramāt / niratiśaya ghana-ghanāghana-ghaṭā-śyāmāyamāna-
27. vāsara-lakṣmī-samārabdha-santata-jalada-samaya-sandehāt / udi(i) eīn
=āneka-narapati-prābhṛitīkrit=āprameya-haya-vāhinī-khara³⁰-khur
=otkhāta-
28. (dhū)lī(i)-dhūsarita³¹-dig=antarālāt parameśvara-sevā-samāyāt = āśeṣa-
Jambudvīpa-bhūpāla-pādātā(a)-bhara³²-namad=avaneḥ Kuddālakḥāta³³-
samā-
29. vāsita-śrīmaj=jayaskandhāvārāt paramasaugata-parameśvara-parama-
bhāṭāraka-mahārājādhirāja-śrī-Devapāladeva-pād=ānudhyātaḥ
30. paramasaugataḥ parameśvaraḥ paramabhāṭārako mahārājādhirājaḥ
śrīmān Mahendrapāladevaḥ kuśalī // Śrī-Puṇḍravarddhana-
31. bhuktau / Ku(ddāla)khāta³⁴-viśaya Nam(n)dadīrghik=oddraṅge sīmā /
Tatra pārvveṇa Ṭaṅgila-nady=arddha-śrotaḥ³⁵ paricchinā dakṣiṇen=āpi
Kubja-gha-

32. ṭikā = 'arddha-śrotikayā Kāśiggada bandhāka³⁶-madhyena Nārāyaṇa-
vāsīya pūrvva-sīm=āvadhīh / Paścimen=āpi Golayi-nirjha(re)-
33. n=Ājagara³⁷-vāsak=āvakhātena vā(a)lmika-stūpen=āśvattha-vṛikṣeṇa³⁸
Svalpa-Nandā(dhā)ra-³⁹paścima-pātena vilva-vṛikṣeṇa Bijjaga-bandhā-
34. kaṃ paścima-Saṅgal=āntar⁴⁰=āmalakī vṛikṣa-paryantaḥ / Uttareṇ=āpy=
ataḥ pūrvvā-mukh=ottara⁴¹-kuṇḍā dakṣiṇena Nandāsūrālyā⁴²
35. Ṭaṅgil=ārdhha-śroto(=')vadhiḥ / Evan=ni(vam ni)yamita-sīmni
samupagatām(n) sarvvān=eva rājanaka-ṛājaputra-kumārāmātya-
bhuktīpa-
36. ti-viśayapati /⁴³ senāpaty=uparika-tadāyuktaka /⁴³ viniyuktaka-dāṇḍika-
daṇḍapāśika /⁴³ caur=oddharaṇika /⁴³ dausādhyasādhā-
37. (nika)-khola-dūta-gamāgamik=ābhivaramāṇa-hasty=aśv=oṣṭra-nau-bala-
vyāpṛitaka-go-mahiṣy=ajāvīkā-vadav=ādhyakṣ=ādi rājapād= opajīvi-
38. no='nyāśa(śca) cāṭa-⁴⁴bhaṭa-jātīyān yathākāl=ādhyāsi-viśaya-
vyavahāriṇaḥ sa-karaṇān (brā)hmana-mānanā-pūrvvakam prativāsi-
39. naḥ kṣetrakarāśa(mśca) yath=ārham=mānāyati bodhayati samādiśati ca
[/*] Matam=astu bhavatām(m) / Mahāsenāpati śrī-Vajradevena dūtaka-
mu-
40. khena vayam=vijñāpitāḥ / Yathā mātā-pitror=ātmanaḥ sakalasya ca
satva-rāśeḥ puṇy=ābhivṛiddhaye Nandadīrghik=odraṅge mayā⁴⁵ vi-

Second Side

41. hāraḥ kāritaḥ tatra yath=oparilikhita-Nandadīrghik=odraṅgam⁴⁶
bhagavato Buddha-bhāṭārakasya Prajñāpāramit=ādi sakala-
42. dharmma-nettrī-sthānasya āry=Āvaiivarttika-Bodhisatva-gaṇasy=āṣṭa-
mahāpuruṣa-pudgal=ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya yath=ārham pūjana-lekha-
43. n=ādy=artham⁴⁷ cīvara-piṇḍapāta-śayan=āś(s)ana-glāna-pratyaya
bhaiṣajya-pariṣkāra=ādy=artham khaṇḍa-sphuṭita-samādhān=ārtha(m)⁴⁸
anye-
44. śam=api mam=ābhimatānām-mat=parikalpita-vibhāgen=ānavadya-
bhog=ārtham śrīmad=Bhāṭāraka-pādā dadatv=iti [/*] Ato='smābhi-
45. s=tadīya⁴⁹vijñāptyā ayaṃ yath=oparilikhita-udraṅgaḥ sva-sambaddha-
bhūmi-sametaś=catus=sīmā-paryantaḥ satalaḥ soddeśaḥ sapa-
46. rikaraḥ saghaṭṭa⁵⁰-tar=opetaḥ sadaś=āpacāraḥ⁵¹ sacaur=oddharaṇaḥ
parihṛita-sarvva-pīḍaḥ /⁵² a-cāṭa-bhaṭa-praveśā(o)='kiñcit= pragrāhyaḥ/

47. rāja-kul=ābhāvya sarvva-pratyāya-sameto bhūmicchidra-nyāyen= ācandr
=ārka-kṣiti-samakālam tath=aiva pradattaḥ /⁵² Yatā(to) bhavadbhi(h)
sarvve(ai)r=eva dāna-
48. m=idam=anumodanīyam prativāsibhiḥ /⁵³kṣetrakaraiś=c=ājña-śravaṇa-
vidheyair=bhūtvā samucita-kara-piṇḍ=ādi pratyāy=opanayaḥ kāryaḥ [/*]
49. Bhāvibhir=api bhūpatibhir=bhūme(r)=ddāna-phala-gauravād= apaharaṇe
mahā naraka-pāta⁵⁴-bhayāc=ca dānam=idam=anumodya paripālanīyam
=i-
50. ti / Samvat 7 Vaiśākha-dine 2 [/*] Tathā ca dharmm=ānuśansana
(śamsinaḥ) ślokāḥ / Vahubhir=vasudhā dattā rājabhiḥ Sagar=ādibhiḥ
[/*] yasya yasya ya-
51. dā bhūmis=tasya tasya tadā phalam(m)/ [//17*] Ṣaṣṭir=vvarṣa-sahasraṇi
svargge modati bhūmidah / ākṣeptā c=ānumantā ca tāny=eva narake
vaset/[18*]
52. Sva-dattām=para-dattām=vā yo hareta vasundharām(m) [/*] sa
viṣṭhāyām kṛi(ri)mir=bhūtvā pitṛibhiḥ saha pacyate [//19*] Iti kamaia-
dal=āmbu-bindu-lolām
53. śriyam=anucintya manuṣya-jīvitāñ=ca [/*] sakalam=idam=udāhṛitañ=
ca buddh(v)ā na hi puruṣaiḥ para-kīrttayo vilopyāḥ [//20*] Śrīmat=
Śaṅgrāma-tā-
54. reṇa kṛitaḥ(te) sukṛita-karmaṇi / Saumitir=iva Rāmeṇ(n)a Śūrapālo
(=')tra dūtakaḥ // [21*] Śrīmān kule mahati Devaradeva-nāmā ślā-
55. ghyo babhūva dharaṇī-tala-gīta-kīrttiḥ / ady=āpi sad=guṇa-kathāsu ya⁵⁵
eka-eva saṁkīrttyate prathamam=eva janair=mmahadbhiḥ [//22*] Anyo-
56. (=')nya-sparddhayā vṛiddham=ananya-jana-gocaram / tyāgas =satyañ=ca
s(ś)auryaṇ=ca yasya c=aitad=guṇa-trayaṁ(m) [//23*] Tasy=ātmajo(=')
bhūt=Kamalā-niv(ā)sah⁵⁶
57. śrīmān sa Nārāyaṇadeva-nāmā [/*] dharmma-priyaḥ prāṇa-samāna-satyo
balena yukto guruṇā mahīyān // [24*] Amalina-taravāri⁵⁷-sphāra-
58. dhārā-nipātaiḥ / pluta-vapur=ari-vṛindam mlānayanāntī samantāt / api kari-
vara-bhed=odbhūta-rakt=ānuliptā diśi diśi sitimānam
59. yasya kīrttis=tatāna [//25*] Tyāgo-nirbhara pu(ū)rit(=ā)rtthi⁵⁸-hṛidayāḥ
sau(śau)ryam jit=ārātikam satya-nirmmita⁵⁹-nāka-dhāma-dhiṣaṇā vijñā-
60. ta-vastu-sthiti(h) / rūpam netra⁶⁰-vinoda-dāna-caturam śīla(m) jan=
ānandakṛit / kīrttir=ddik=sarasīṣu kairava-vanac=chāy=eva yasy=ābhavat
[//26*]

61. Vahnir=vvair=īndhanānām nn(n)aya⁶¹-śata-mukūṣ=odghṛiṣṭa-pād=
āravindah pātā loka-sthitinām(m) praṇayi-jana-saroj=ākar=
ārkaḥyamaṇ(n)ah / yah pri-
62. thyām=ekanāthaḥ prathita-nija-guṇa-ślaghayā varjjit=ātmā [/*] cakre śrī-
Darmmapālo nripatir=adhipatim=maṇḍale Darddaraṇḍyām(m)⁶² // [27*]
Babhūva
63. Lakṣmīr=iva tasya jāyā vapus=trī(ri)lokī-tilakam=vahantī / siddhi-
sr(stri)i-varggasya vapuṣmet=īva /⁶³ Kalyāṇadev = īti yath=ā(r)ttha-nāmā
// [28*] K(u)la-kama-
64. linī-lilā-Lakṣmīr=ut=ālaya-devatā sva-pati-hṛidaya-grāhiny=esā satī kim
=Arundhatī [/*] Kim=uta Vasudhār=eyam=iva vitta-prasādhitā-
mandirā
65. iti manasi y=āviṣṭā(n) lokāmś=cakāra vitarkkitān [//29*] Div=īva tasyām
raviṇ=eva tena dhām=eva⁶⁴ samyag=vidhin=odapādi⁶⁵ / satv=opakār=
aika-ra-
66. taḥ pratāpī śrī-Vajradevo vimala-svabhāvaḥ [//30*] Yo Lakṣmīr=
kulajān=dadhat⁶⁶=praṇayinīm=vīry=odayāl=līlayā khaḍg=āvarjjita danti-
kumbha-vi-
67. galad=rakt=āmbubhiḥ /⁶⁷ plāvitaḥ / hutvā śastra-hutāsane ripu-havir=
mmantr=ānvito durllabhām saṅgrāme Vija(ya)-śriyam=pariṇayan=loke
varatvam(m) gataḥ // [31*]
68. (Tyā)go dravo ca⁶⁸ satye sadasi paṭu-giror=n=āpavāde parasya⁶⁹ / prañā
śāstre na jātu⁷⁰ vyapagata-tamaso vañcane(=')pi praj=ārthāḥ⁷¹ / kṣāntir
=dāne⁷²na (bhūyo)
69. dviṣati raṇa-vare sammukhe śastra-pāṇau / maitrī-tyāge sthire(o=')-
bhūn=na tu cala vanitā-samprayoge (=') pi yasya // [32*] Āryeṣu Jahnu-
tanayā śa(sa)-
70. lil=ābhīṣeko dik=kāminīṣu ghana-candana-paṅka-lepaḥ [/*] Durvvāra-
vairi-vanitā-vadan=āmbujeṣu⁷³ yasy=endu-dhāma⁷⁴-kalito yaśasām
vitānaḥ [//33*]
71. Han(m)sasy=aitāḥ⁷⁵ prakṛiti-paṭavo yāvad=ev=eha gāvaḥ / tatv=ālokaṁ
vihata-tamasah tan(v)ate sarvva-dikkaṁ⁷⁶ / yāvat=prī-
72. thvī-valaya-vahan=āścarya-karmma(ā) ca Ku(ū)rmmaḥ / tāvat=tasya
vrajatu kṛitinaḥ kīrttir=esā pratiṣṭhām(m) [//34*]
73. Utkīrṇam=idam śāsanam sāmanta-śrī-Māhaṭena⁷⁷ /

Translation

Verses (1-16):

Success. Hail! May the illustrious *Sugata* (the Buddha, literally, one who has fared well), whose teaching is respected (*mānita-sāsano*), who occupies his exalted seat by virtue of his (spiritual) power (*nijabalair=adhyāsito*), is full of virility (*vīryavān*), is lord of joy (*ary=ānanda*), one whose mind¹ is happy with energy derived from inherent gift² (*sva-bhūti-nanditamānā*), one who is fond of bestowing gifts (*dāna-priyaḥ*), who is forebearing (*kṣāntimān*), who was born in a lustrous race (*bhāsvad=vaṁśa-bhavaḥ*), who works for the well-being of his subjects (*prajā-hita-karo*), is the exclusive lord of the entire world (*niḥśeṣa-bhūmīśvaraḥ*), is Siddhārtha (literally, one who has fulfilled the object of his coming), and is the upholder of righteousness (*pātā ca dharmma-sthiteḥ*), protect the worlds (*bhuvanāni pātu*).—V. 1.

Here was born a king (*nṛpatir=iha babhūva*) named *Gopāla* (*Gopāla-nāmā*), who was the abode of brightness (*dhāmnān=dhūma*) and was, like the sun, expert (*ravir=iva paṭu*) in destroying the darkness of night (*dhvasta-doṣ=āndhakāro*). Innumerable gems of quality (*agaṇita-guṇa-ratnam*) grew on account of him (*yam sam=āsādyā jātā(am)*). The goddess of fortune (*Śrīḥ*) gave oblations of water (*datta-toy=āñjalih*) to the comforts of the abode of Hari (*Hari-Vasati-sukhebhyo*).—V. 2.

His son was the illustrious *Dharmapāla* (*Śrī-Dharmmapāla-iti tasya suto babhūva*) who obtained fortune (*jay=ārjjita-Śrīḥ*) by defeating the forces of extremely arrogant foes (*aty=uddhata-dviṣad=anika*). The impurities of the great darkness of Kali (*Kali-santamas=āvilāni*) were washed away (*prakṣālitāni*) clearing the faces of the directions (*kakubhām=mukhāni*) by his moon-like fame³ (*yasy=endun=eva yaśasū*).—V. 3.

Having defeated in battle (*vijitya samare*) stubborn enemies (*durvārān dviṣato*) including *Indrarāja* (*Indrarāj=ādikān*); and churning violently (*pramathya*), the lord of the Sindhus (*Sindhūnām=adhipam*), the latter was per force compelled to come forth (*rabhasād=unmīlita*) by the king (*kṣmābhṛitā*). His own territory (*nijā mahī*) *Mahodaya* (*Mahodayavatī*) was given away by the valourous one (*vikrāntbhājā*) to the unpretentious (*nirvyāja*) supplicant *Cakrāyudha* (*Cakrāyudh=ārthine*), as was done by Bali to the begging *Vāmana*⁴ (*Balin=ānati-Vāmanāya*).—V. 4.

Pollens of flowers (or particles of toiletry) from his courtyard (*reṇūn yasy=āṅganebhyo*) which were being blown by the air breathed (*śvasa-vātā haranti*) by the queens of the slain enemies⁵ (*hata-ripu-mahiṣī*) were sprinkled clear (*siñcanti=etāni*) by the streams of water in the shape of echor discharged

The Jagjibanpur Plate of Mahendrapāla Comprehensively Re-edited

from the temples of rutting elephants (*mādyat-kari-karaṭa-toya-galad=dāna-toya-pravāhāḥ*). He (*Dharmmapāla*) held the lotus-hands of *Lakṣmī* (*Lakṣmī-kara-kamala-dhṛitaḥ*) brought by his immense power (*daurddapy=ānīta*) and his lotus-like feet were worshipped (*pūjitaḥ pāda-padmaḥ*) by the kings attending on him bowing down in salutation (*rājñām sevāparāṇām=pranata*) with the jewels adorning their crowns appearing like flower-wreaths (*nija-siro-ratna-puspa-pratānāḥ*).—V. 5.

The pleasure-house of Morality (*Nīter=vvilāsa-bhavanam*) and the darling of Valour⁶ (*priya Vikramāyāḥ*), the illustrious *Devapāla*, was his son. Seeking to see (i.e. to ascertain) the range of the world out of curiosity (*kautukād=iva jagat=padavīn=didṛikṣu*), he wandered about (*cankramyate sma*) the earth playfully as if it were the quadrangle (*bhavan=āṅgana-līlay=eva*) of his own house.—V. 6.

The stage-director of the drama of great wars (*mahā-samara-nātaka-sūtradhāraḥ*), with the golds (i.e. wealth) of the kings of the world collected by expeditions (*daṇḍ=opanīta-kanakair=vasudh=ādhipānām*), built a temple of *Sugata* (*Sugata-sadma*) and an abode of *Gaurī* (*gṛihañ=ca Gauryāḥ*) which was an object of curiosity⁷ (*kautukañ=ca*) and an ornament (literally, a mark on the forehead, *tilakañ=ca*) of the three worlds (*jagat=traye'pi*).—V. 7.

Fierce battle razed with clanking of armour and discharge of fierce weapons (*durvvār=āstra-nipāta-bhīṣaṇa-raṇat-sannāha labdh=odayam*). The sun was made witness (*sākṣīkritya vibhāvasum*) in the great pavilion (*mahā-maṇḍape*) with its elevated sacrificial war altar of human heads (*raṇa-siro-vedī*) in which the enemies' array of elephants, overcome with swords (*khadg=āvarjjita-vairi-vāraṇa-satā*) had their pot-like heads pierced with arrows (or spears) and flowing with blood (*kumbhā-sṛig=ambhhaḥ-pluto*). The supreme lord of the world (*kṣitīśvaravaro*) collected tributes (*jagrāha karam*) from kings of the entire world (*niḥśeṣa-bhūbhṛid= bhuvām*).—V. 8.

The enemies who fought him (*yodhayāmāsur=arātayas=te*) were those who had lust for the celestial damsels (*yeṣām riraṁsā sura-sundarībhiḥ*) and hence they reached up to the travel course of the sun (*vivasvad=bhramaṇ=āvadhīni*) in their bid to buy the objects of their desire, viz. fame (*kretum =iṣṭāny=asubhir= yaśāmsī*).—V. 9.

(a) By whom (*yena*, i.e. by Śiva), immense spiritual power was forever held/or sacrificial ashes were perpetually worn (*vipulām=bhūtiñ=ciram=bibhratā*) with the generation (through penance) of dharma (*dharmmasya prasavena*); by being capable of robbing the beauty of *Kāma* (the god of love: *hṛita-Kāma-rūpa-vibhavana*), reducing it to ashes with the play of his eye-brows (*bhrū-lilā*), to put on the same for his primary adornment

(ārohat=ādyam=bhūṣam); by holding in marriage the laudable hand (ślāghyaṅ=karaṅ=grihnatā) of Durgā (=Pārvatī), the daughter of the mountain Himālaya (Himālay=ācala-bhuvah), perfection of self (samyak=svam) and supreme divinity (parameśvaratvam) were shown by the unsurpassed god (aparan=devena sandarśitam).—V. 10.

(b) By whom (yena, i.e. by Devapāla), immense power was for long possessed (vipulām-bhūtiṅ=ciram=bibhratā) through his birth from Dharmapāla (Dharmasya prasavena)⁸; by being capable of robbing Kāmarūpa⁹ (Assam; hṛita-kāmarūpa-vibhavana) within the twinkle of an eye (i.e. quickly and effortlessly: (bhrū-līlā), which was his first attainment (ārohat=ādyam =bhūṣam); by exacting coveted tributes (ślāghyaṅ=karaṅ=grihnatā) from inaccessible regions of the Himalayas¹⁰ (durggāyās=ca Himālay=ācala-bhuvah) - perfection of self (samyak=svam) and supreme divinity (parameśvaratvam)¹¹ were shown by this other god (i.e. Devapāla : aparan=devena sandarśitam).—V. 10.

He, the lord of men (narendrah), married (ūḍha) Māhaṭā, who was chaste (sādhvīm), a follower of the path of righteousness (dharmaaparām), bore auspicious physical features (sulakṣaṅ-āṅgīm), was an embodiment of the Tretā age¹² (Traitīm), as it were, and was the daughter (sutām) of the king Durlabharāja (Durlabharāja-nāmaḥ), a (veritable) moon in the ocean of the lineage of the Cāhamānas (Cāhamān=ānvaya-vāridh=īndoh).—V. 11.

She, like Devakī (sā Devak=īva), gave birth to the best of all sons, Mahendrapāla (sut=ottamam=asūta Mahendrapālam) who was adored by thousands of men and divinities (nara-deva-sahasra-vandyam), who bore the burden of the earth with ease (saukaryato vasumatī-bharam=udvahantam), was chosen by Lakṣmī as lord (husband) on her own accord (Lakṣmyāḥ svayamvara-patim), was a divinity (devam) and the most perfect man (puruṣ=ottamam).—V. 12.

On the dust (rajasām) kicked up on account of his marching for the conquest of the regions (yasy=āsā-vijaya-prayāṇe) having moved upwards and lain thick in arrays filling the entire sky (sāndre upasarppati vyūhe nirbhara-pūrit= āmbaratayā), creating a false likeness of the earth¹³ (sampādit=orvvī-bhrame), the groups of Vidyādhara (Vidyādharāṅgāṃ gaṅgāḥ), on touching it with the soles of their feet (sprīṣṭaiḥ pādatalaiḥ) were filled with the apprehension of falling down unexpectedly (akāṅḍe patan=āśaṅkā) and muttered (ajapan) attributing to some astonishing trick (camatkāriṇī-vidyām) the only cause of this flying upwards (utpatan=aika-hetum).—V. 13.

From the snow-clad mountain (ā-prāleya-gireḥ) with the sign of the bull (vriṣāṅka) having the tops of its gem-bearing site stamped exposed by

the hooves of the bull (vriṣabha-kṣuṇṇ=āgra-ratna-sthalād); from the sea (ā-sindhoḥ) the inner water of which had been stirred up by the arrows of the enemy of the Ten-headed one (Daśa-kandhar=āri-viśikha-vyāloḍit=āntarjjalāt); and from the two mountains (śaila-dvayāt) which are the two ornaments, each of the eastern and western directions (ā-pūrvv=āpara-diṅ=mukh=aika-tilakāt), kings unpretentiously fall down (bhūbhujā nirvyājam nipatanti) at his feet (yasya carane) with their crowns (or heads) lowered down from a distance (dūr=ānatair=mmaulibhiḥ).—V. 14.

The blood flowing (vigalat kīlāla) from the temples of mighty elephants (mah=ebha-kumbha) felled down by sword (khaḍg=otkhāta) turned into a stream (dhārā jale) being increased in volume with the addition of water in the shape of tears (vāṣp=āmbubhiḥ varddhitah) shed by the eyes of the enemies' wives (vairi-vadhū-vilocana-vamad). Even swimming across the lords of waters (santīry=āpi patīn=apām), it moved out in every direction with thousands of mouths (pratidiśam yātam sahasrair=mmukhaiḥ). The fire of his prowess (yasya pratāp=ānalah) shone wonderfully (vilasito) blended alike (citram) with fierceness and pathos (vādhaka-kāruṇ(y)aiḥ).—V. 15.

“Oh moon among kings (nṛipati-candra), are ever (sarvādā) craved for by the fortune of victory (jaya-śriy=ārthī); not even in dreams (svapne'pi na) have I (the Goddess of Victory) become your beloved (praṇayinī bhavato ='ham= āsam)”. Thus (ittham) by her propitiating the foes (ripūn bhajantyā) out of fear and anger (bhīyā kupitay=eva), his pleasures in the war-games (samara-keli-sukhāni yasya) were killed¹⁴ (vyājaghnire).—V. 16.

Prose Portion: (Divided into Sections A to G by us)

A. Lines 25-30: (Sa khalu Bhāgīrathī-patha...Mahendrapāladevaḥ kuśalī)

From the prosperous and victorious camp pitched at Kuddālakṣātaka,¹⁵ where the fleets of boats of various kinds moving along the course of the Bhāgīrathī, by giving rise to a semblance of a series of sunken mountain tops and consequently of the building of another Setubandha ; where the darkening of the brightness of daylight by packed arrays of rutting elephants seems to raise the suspicion of (the onset of) the incessant rainy season; where the horizon is rendered grey by the dust dug up by the hard hooves of innumerable troops of horses presented by many kings of the north; and where the earth is pressed down under the weight of the infantry of the countless kings of Jambudvīpa gathered to pay homage to their supreme lord, the devout worshipper of Sugata, Parameśvara, Parama-bhaṭṭāraka, Mahārājādhirāja, the illustrious Mahendrapāladeva, who meditates on the feet of the devout worshipper of Sugata, Parameśvara, Paramabhaṭṭāraka, Mahārājādhirāja,

the illustrious *Devapāladeva*, being in good health (makes the present announcement)

B. Lines 30-35: (*Śrī-Pauṇḍravarddhana-bhuktauṬangil=ārdha-ś(s) roto (') vadhih*)

The boundaries in respect of the *Nandadīrghikā udraṅga* comprised in the *Kuddālakhātaka viṣaya* under the illustrious *Puṇḍravarddhana-bhukti*:

There the half stream of the river *Ṭangila* marks the boundary on the east and (partly) on the south too, which is (further) demarcated by the half stream of *Kubja-ghaṭikā*, *Kāśiggadu-bandhāka* in the middle, stretching up to the eastern boundary of *Nārāyaṇa-vāsa*. The western boundary is marked by *Golayi nirjjhara*, the low land (*avakhāta*) of *Ajagara-vāsaka* (python habitat), termite-mound, *aśvattha* tree (the holy fig tree, *Ficus Religiosa*), the western bank (*paścima pāṭa*) of *Svalpanandādhāra*,¹⁶ the *vilva* tree (*Aegle Marmelos*, *bel*), west of *Bijjaga-bandha*, the *āmalakī* tree (*Emblic Myrobalam*) six reeds away¹⁷ (*ṣaṇ=ṇal=āntara*). Next, the northern boundary consists of the east-facing northern water-holes, and (the area) from *Nandasurāli* on the south upto the half stream of (the river) *Ṭangila*.

C. Lines 35-39 : (*Evan=niyamita-sīmni samupāgatān....sam=ādiśati ca*)

To all the people assembled within the specified boundary, viz. the *rājanaka* (feudatory), *rājaputra* (prince or a subordinate ruler), *kumārāmātya* (an officers' cadre composed originally of junior members of the royal family), *bhuktipati* (an officer in charge of a bhukti, i.e. an administrative unit, a province), *viṣayapati* (the governor of a district, *viṣaya*), *senāpati* (a military commander, or the commander-in-chief), *uparika* (a viceroy, the governor of a province; the word literally means 'one at the top'), *tadāyuktaka* (an officer who was subordinate to *āyuktaka*, an officer, often the governor of a district or subdivision), *vinīyuktaka* (a subordinate officer under the *āyuktaka*), *daṇḍika* (a police officer), *daṇḍapāśika* (a policeman), *caur=oddharaṇika* (police officer in charge of recovery of stolen goods), *dauḥsādhyā-sādhanika* (officers trained to undertake daring feats¹⁸ of civilian or military nature), *khola* (officer, the nature of whose job is uncertain), *dūta* (messenger), *gamāgamika* (probably an officer in charge of regulating the people's entrance and departure in cities or the royal court), *abhitvaramāṇa* (letter-carrier or a special kind of messenger, one who expedited work), *hasty=aśv=oṣṭra-nau-bala-vyāpṛitaka* (military officers in charge of elephants, horses, camels, the army and the navy), *gomahiṣy=a-jāvikā-vaḍav=ādhyakṣa* (superintendents looking after cows, she-buffaloes, goats and mares), and others subsisting on the king's feet (i.e. under the employment of the king) as well as those falling under the categories of

cātas (irregular soldiers), *bhaṭas* (literally, soldiers, but really constables) and the district officers (*viṣaya vyavahāriṇaḥ*) including the *karaṇas* (accountant, clerk or scribe), as may be present from time to time (*yathākāl=ādhyāsi*) and to the resident cultivators¹⁹ (*prativāsinaḥ kṣetrakarāṁś=ca*) - to all these, especially honouring the *brāhmaṇas*, he (i.e. king Mahendrapāla) pays due respect, makes known, and issues these commands:

D. Lines 39-44: (*Matam=astu bhavatām...Śrīmad=Bhaṭṭarakapādā dadatv=iti*)

'May it have your consent. We have been informed by the *Mahāsenāpati* (the great commander of the forces), the illustrious *Vajradeva*, through the mouth of the *dūta* (emissary of the grant) as follows':

'I have caused a *vihāra* (Buddhist monastery) to be constructed in *Nandadīrghikā udraṅga* (*Nandadīrghik=odraṅge mayā vihāraḥ kāritaḥ*) for the enhancement of the religious merit of my mother and father, myself and the whole multitude of living beings. May his Gracious Majesty (literally, the feet of his Gracious Majesty - 'Bhaṭṭarakapādā(ḥ)') grant²⁰ (*dadatu*) the *Nandadīrghikā udraṅga*²¹ as written above for worship (*pūjana*), writing/copying²² (of Buddhist religious texts - 'lekhana'), etc.; garments (for monks - 'civara'), food/alms (for monks-*piṇḍapāta*), beds (*śayana*), seats (*āsana*), requisites for the sick (*glāna-pratyaya*), medicines (*bhaiṣajya*), other requisites (for monks - *pariṣkāra*) etc. (*ādy=ārtham*); for repair of damages and cracks, etc. (of the *vihāra* - 'khaṇḍa-sphutita-samādhān=ārtham)—as fit/applicable ('yath-ārtham')— of the divine lord Buddha (*Bhagavato Buddha-bhaṭṭarakasya*); the category of *Prajñāpāramitā* and all the other female religious leaders/divinities (*Prajñāpāramit=ādi-sakala-dharmma-nettrī-sthānasya*); the group of *Bodhisatvas* of the noble *Avaiarttika* order (*āry=Āvaiarttika-Bodhisatva-gaṇasya*); the noble congregation of monks adhering to the individual eight holy personages (*aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgala-ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya*); as also for the unblemished enjoyment (*anavadya-bhog=ārtham*) with the apportionment (of facilities / land) made according to my plan (*mat-parikalpita-vihāgena*), also of others of my choice²³ (*anyeṣām=api mam=ābhimatānām*)'.

E. Lines 44-47: (*Ato='smābhis=tadīya vijñāptyā...tath=aiva pradattaḥ*)

Thereupon, in pursuance of his submission (*tadīya vijñāptyā*), the *udraṅga* as written above has been accordingly granted by us²⁴ (*asmābhiḥ.... tath=aiva pradattaḥ*) with (adjacent) land attached thereto within the four specified boundaries (*sva-sambaddha bhūmi-sametaś=catus=sīmā-paryantaḥ*) with (right of) the bottom and the surface (*satalaḥ soddeśaḥ*), *uparikara* (additional taxes), with ghats (landing quays) with boats²⁵ (*sa-ghaṭṭa-tar=opetaḥ*), with the ten offences (*sa-daś=āpacāraḥ*) with recovery of stolen articles from

thieves (*sa-caur=oddharanaḥ*), with exemption from all oppressions (*parihṛita-sarva-pīdaḥ*), free from the entry of cāṭas and bhāṭas (*a-cāta-bhāṭa-praveśaḥ*), totally exempted from payment of taxes (*a-kiñcit-pragrāhyaḥ*), together with all the income which will no longer be the royal family's due, in accordance with the *bhūmicchidra-nyāya* (the principle of rent-free enjoyment of uncultivable land), to last as long as the moon, the sun and the earth shall endure (*ā-candr=ārka-kṣiti-sama-kālam*).

F. Lines 47-50 : (*Yatā(o) bhavadbhiḥ sarvvair=eva.... dharmm=ānuśansana ślokāḥ*)

Wherefore this grant should be approved by all. And the resident cultivators, being ready to obey our commands, should make over (to the donee) the customary taxes, payments in kind and other types of revenue (*samucita-kara-piṇḍ=ādi pratyāy=opanayaḥ kāryaḥ*).

Furthermore, the future kings, out of respect for the merit accruing from a gift of land, and afraid of falling into the great hell consequent on the resumption of it, should applaud and preserve this gift.

(Issued in the) year (samvat) 7 on the Vaiśākha day 2.

There are also verses in praise of dharmma:

Land has been given away by many kings like Sagara and others. Whosoever (king) at any given time owns the land, to him accrues the merit (of such grant) at the time. -V. 17.

The giver of land enjoys in heaven for sixty thousand years and the transgressor (of a grant as well as the conniver of such transgression) dwells in hell for the same number of years. -V. 18.

He, who misappropriates land given either by himself or by others, rots along with his forefathers as worms in excreta. -V. 19.

The good deeds of others should not be obliterated by people pondering that fortune as well as human life is fickle like a drop of water on a lotus petal, and also comprehending all that has been cited herein. -V. 20.

Śūrapāla has been made the emissary (*Śūrapāl=otra dūtakaḥ*) in this meritorious act (*sukṛita-karmaṇi*) by the illustrious Star/Saviour in Wars²⁷ (*Śrīmat-saṅgrāmatāreṇa*), like the son of Sumitrā by Rāma (*Saumitrir=iva Rāmeṇa*). -V. 21.

In a great family (*kule mahati*) was born an illustrious person (*Śrīmān*), Devaradeva by name (*Devaradeva-nāmā*), who possessed an enviable reputation (*ślāghya*) and whose fame was sung across the world (*dharaṇī-talagīta-kīrttiḥ*). Even today (*adyāpi*), talking about virtues (*sad=guṇa=kathāsu*), he alone is the subject of the praises sung at the very beginning (*eka-eva samkīrttyate prathamameva*) by eminent people (*janair=mmahadbhiḥ*). -V. 22.

Sacrifice, truthfulness and valour (*tyāgaḥ satyañ=ca śauryañ=ca*)-these three virtues of his (*yasya c=aitad=guṇa-trayam*)=grew vying with one another (*anny='onya-sparddhayā vṛiddham*) as is not noticed in any other person²⁸ (*ananya-jana-gocaram*). -V. 23.

His son, the illustrious Nārāyaṇadeva by name (*tasy=ātmajo='bhūt Śrīmān sa Nārāyaṇadeva-nāmā*), was the abode of Kamalā (*Kamalā-nivāsaḥ*). A lover of righteousness (*dharmma-priyaḥ*), to him truth was as dear as his life (*prāṇa-samāna-satyo*). He possessed great physical strength (*balena yukto*) and was considered highly by his teacher²⁹ (*guruṇā mahīyān*). -V. 24.

The multitude of his enemies, their bodies streaming with blood split by the ceaseless and fierce blows of his spotless sword (*amalina-taravāri-sphāradhārā-nipātaiḥ*), are fading all around (*mlānayanī samantāt*). Though smeared with blood (*rakt=ānuliptā*) from the great pierced elephants (*api kari-vara-bhedo*), his fame spread over the different directions rendering them white (*diśi diśi sitimānam yasya Kīrttis=tatāna*). -V. 25.

The heart of supplicants was filled (by him) depending on (personal) sacrifice (*tyāgo-nirbhara-pūrit=ārthi-hṛidayāḥ*); the enemies were conquered with valour (*śauryaṃ jit=ārātikam*); the heavenly abode (for himself) was built with truthfulness (*satya-nirmīta-nāka-dhāma*); the (true) position of matters was ascertained by intellect (*dhiṣaṇā vijñāta-vastu-sthitiḥ*). His graceful appearance was apt to give pleasure to the eyes (*rūpaṃ netra-vinoda-dāna-caturam*), conduct lent happiness to the people³¹ (*śīlam jan=ānandakṛit*). His fame (*kīrttiḥ*) was like the reflection of a forest of white lotuses (*kairava-vana-cchāy=eva yasy=ābhavat*) in the lake of the quarters (*dik-sarasīsu*). -V. 26.

He was (like) fire unto the faggots (in the shape) of the enemies (*vahnir=vvair=īndhanānām*) and rubbed his white lotus-like feet (*udghṛiṣṭa-pād=āravindaḥ*) against hundreds of (royal) crowns which had been taken (*naya-śata-mukūṭa*) from them. He was the protector of the established social order (*pātā loka-sthitiṇām*) and to the (lotus-like) beloved ones he stood for the sun, the caterer for lotuses (*praṇayi-jana-saroj=ākar=ārkāyamānaḥ*). The sole lord of the earth (*prithvyām=eka-nāthaḥ*), he turned self-effacing (*varjjit=ātmā*) in the face of praises of his well-reputed qualities (*prathita-nija-guṇa-Slāghayā*). The illustrious king Dharmapāla made him chief (ruler) of the maṇḍala of Darddaraṇḍī³² (*Śrī-Dharmmapālo nṛipatir=adhipatim=maṇḍale Darddaraṇḍyām*). -V. 27.

His wife, like Lakṣmī (Lakṣmī=iva tasya jāyā), was an embodiment of the three worlds (*vapus=trilokī*) and constituted (by virtue of her extraordinary qualities) the distinctive mark on the forehead thereof (*tilakam=vahantī*). In her, the three-fold categories of human endeavour reached their fulfilment

(siddhis=tri-varggasya) and appropriately was she named Kalyānadevī (Kalyānadev=īti yath = ārttha-nāmā). -V. 28

'Is she a kindred of Lakṣmī sporting playfully among the lotuses (*kula-kamalinī-lilā-Lakṣmīḥ*), or is she the presiding deity of the house (*ut=ālaya-devatā*) or is this chaste lady,³³ the capturer of the heart of her husband (*sva-pati-grāhiny=eṣā satī*) Arundhatī (*kim=Arundhatī*), or is this female temple, embellished with wealth (*vitta-prasādhitā-mandirā*), the Earth herself (*Vasudhār=eyam*)?' She gave rise to such debates in the minds of the people who were engrossed (*iti manasi y=āviṣṭā(n) lokāms=cakāra vitarkitān*). -V. 29.

On her (Kalyānadevī), who was like the sky (*div=īva tasyām*), was begotten (*udapādi*) by him (Nārāyaṇadeva), who was like the sun (*ravin=eva tena*), a son, viz. the illustrious Vajradeva, the abode of perfection by the creator³⁴ (*dhām=eva samyag=vidhinā*). Valiant (*pratāpī*), single-minded in doing good to (all) living beings (*satv=opakār=aika-rataḥ*), he possesses an unblemished nature³⁵ (*vimala-svabhāvaḥ*). -V. 30.

He gained at ease (*līlayā*) possession of his beloved (*dadhat=pranayinīm*) Lakṣmī of noble birth (*Lakṣmīn=kulajām*) with the rise of his power (*vīry=odayāt*); flooded (the battlefield) with water (in the shape) of blood (*rakt=āmbubhiḥ plāvitaḥ*) flowing from the temples of tuskers (*danti-kumbha-vigalat*) which were brought down by his sword (*khadg=āvarjjita*). He reached celebrity in the world (*loke varatvam gataḥ*) by marrying (*pariṇayan*) the rarely attainable (*durllabhām*) goddess of victory³⁶ (*Vijaya-śriyam*) in battle (*saṅgrāme*) in which the enemies took the place of clarified butter for oblation (*ripu-haviḥ*), and, with chanting of incantations (*mantr.=ānvito*) were offered (*hutvā*) unto the (sacrificial) fire (in the shape of arms (*śastra-hutāśane*). -V. 31.

Passionate and swift in truth (*rāgo dravo ca satye*), he is an expert of oration before the public (*sadasī paṭu-giroḥ*) and not in spreading calumny about others (*n=āpavāde parasya*). His proficiency in the scriptures (*prajñā śāstre*) never keeps away from darkness (*na jātu vyapagata-tamaso*) and the subjects' cause does not suffer even in deception (*vañcane='pi praj=ārthāḥ*) There is no let up in charity (*kṣāntir=dāne na bhuyo*) and he confronts the enemy only in proper war when he (the enemy) is armed (*dviṣati raṇavare sammukhe śastra-pāṇau*). He was steady in friendship and sacrifice (*maitrī-tyāge sthiro='bhut*) there would be no wavering (*na tu cala*) even when in contact with women³⁷ (*vanitā-samprayoge='pi yasya*). -V. 32.

The (canopy-like) spread of his fame, furnished with the lustre of the moon³⁸ (*yasy=endu=dhāma-kalito yaśasām vitānaḥ*) over the lotus faces of the wives of the irresistible enemies (*durvvāra-vairi-vanitā-vadan=āmbujeṣu*)

is (so much to their liking) like consecration in the holy water of the Gaṅgā (literally, the holy water of Jahnu's daughter: *Jahnu-tanayā-salil=ābhiṣeko*) to the nobles (*āryeṣu*), and like anointment with thick sandal-wood paste (*ghana-candana-panka-lepaḥ*) to the maidens of the quarters (*dik=kāminīṣu*). -V. 33.

As long as these skies of the goose,³⁹ skilled by nature (in directing the goose to its course) endure (*hansasy=aitāḥ prakṛiti=patavo yāvad=ev=eha gāvaḥ*); the light of truth (*tattv=ālokaḥ*), the dispeller of darkness (*vihata-tamaseḥ*), illuminates all the directions (*tanvate sarvva-dikkaḥ*); and as long as the Tortoise-the performer of the extraordinary feat of bearing the volume of the earth (*yāvat-prithvī-valaya-vahan=āścarya-karmā*) lasts, so long may this meritorious act⁴⁰ (as recorded in this grant) of the achiever go on to attract fame (*tāvat=tasya vrajatu kṛitinaḥ kīrttir=eṣā pratiṣṭhām*). -V. 34.

Prose Portion:

G. Line 73: (*Utkīrṇam=idam Śrī-Māhaṭena*)

This (copper plate) charter has been engraved (*utkīrṇam = idam śāsanam*) by the feudatory chief, the illustrious Māhaṭa⁴¹ (*sāmanta-Śrī-Māhaṭena*).

Discussion And Analysis

Auspicious beginning : line 1

Like other copper plate inscriptions of the Pāla kings, the present one begins with an auspicious symbol, standing for 'siddham' or 'siddhir=astu'. This is followed by the auspicious word 'svasti' (hail).

First phase of verses : 1-16 (lines 1-25).

The inscription then takes to verses in the way characteristic of Pāla copper-plate inscriptions. There are altogether 16 verses in the first phase occurring in lines 1 to 25. None of these appears in any other Pāla inscription.

Invocation of Siddhārtha : Verse 1

The first verse makes an invocation of Siddhārtha, also called Sugata (i.e. the Buddha, the family deity of the Pālas).

The epithets applied to the Buddha here are : (1) mānita-śāsana, (2) nija-balair = adhyāsita, (3) vīryavān, (4) ary=ānanda, (5) sva-bhūti-nanditamanā (6) dāna-priya, (7) kṣāntimān, (8) bhāsvad-varṁśa-bhava, (9) prajā-hita-kara, (10) niḥśeṣa-bhūm=iśvara, and (11) pātā (ca) dharmma-stihiteḥ.

Unlike in some other Pāla c.ps, no apparent attempt has been made here to extol the virtues of any particular Pāla king simultaneously by using words of double entendre.¹

Genealogical Verses - Gopāla (I) to Mahendrapāla : Verses 2-16**King Gopāla (I) : Verse 2.**

The second verse eulogises Gopāla as the source of brightness, and as expert (paṭu=read as paṭa by others) like the sun in dispelling the darkness of night, which may bear allusion to the dark period of 'mātsyanyāya'².

Innumerable gems of quality grew on account of him (agaṇita-guṇa-ratnaṃ yaṃ sam=āsādyā jātā (am), which induced Śrī (i.e. Lakṣmī) to give oblations of water (datta-toy=āñjali-Śrīḥ) to the comforts of the abode of Hari (Hari-vasati-sukhebhya). Kamala Kanta Gupta's rendering that 'he (Gopāla I) conquered the region upto the sea' is unwarranted.³

King Dharmmapāla: verses 3-5

The next three verses (verses 3-5) dwell on Dharmapāla, the son and successor of Gopāla I.

Verse 3 states that fortune (Śrīḥ) was obtained by Dharmapāla by conquering the forces of extremely arrogant foes. The impurities of the great darkness of Kali (i.e. the Kali Age) were washed away and the faces of the directions were cleared up by his moon-like fame ('yasy=endun=eva-yaśasā', wrongly read as 'yasy=Endrandeva yaśasā' by R&I, and SCM).

Verse 4 refers to the defeat at the hands of Dharmapāla of stubborn enemies (durvvārān dviṣato) including Indrarāja (Indrarāj=ādikān). It is further stated that Dharmapāla gave away his own territory (nijā mahī) including Mahodaya (Mahodayavati) to the unpretentious (nirvyāja) supplicant Cakrāyudha (Cakrāyudh=ārthine) as had been done by Bali to the begging Vāmana (Balin=ānati-Vāmanāya)⁴. Indrarāja here obviously refers to Indrāyudha, Cakrāyudha's rival claimant to the throne of Kanauj, whose causes was espoused by the other north Indian power-house of the time who also possessed imperial ambitions, viz., the Gurjara-Pratīhāras.⁵

The same verse (V.4) also claims some sort of victory obtained by Dharmapāla over the king of the Sindhu region (then under Muslim occupation), but its precise nature is not quite clear. The king of the 'Yavanas' finds mention among the north Indian kings who attended the durbar at Kanauj as subordinates of Dharmapāla (Khalimpur c.p.). The word 'unmilita' (not 'unmūlita' as read by some scholars) leaves the position somewhat unclear, though the words 'pramatyya' and rabhasā' seem to indicate the use of force on Dharmapāla's part on the king of Sindhu. The matter must remain inconclusive for the present.

In verse 5 the composer has endeavoured to show his poetic skill while

indicating the might of Dharmapāla. The queens of the slain enemies (not 'the dying queens' as translated by R&I) were kept confined by Dharmapāla; the particles of dust (reṇūn) or pollen or toiletry (given up by them as a mark of their widowhood), which were blown by their breath (i.e. sigh), were sprinkled clear by the streams of ichor flowing down the temples of the rutting elephants (of the Pāla king).

King Devapāla : verses 6 to 10.

Verse 8 : It is distressing to see how scholar after scholar failed to correctly interpret the expression 'Nīter=vvilāsa-bhavanam=priya-Vikramāyaḥ Śrī-Devapāla-iti tat=tanayo babhūva', until its correct significance was made clear by Gouriswar Bhattacharya.⁶ Failing to realise that the attributes relate to Devapāla and not to Dharmapāla, these scholars became unduly concerned about a supposed 'Vikramā' being a (second) queen of Dharmapāla, co-wife of Raṇṇādevī (mother of Devapāla)⁷:

As has been pointed out by GB in clarifying the expression, a parallel expression, 'naya-vikram=aika-vasatiḥ' has been used in respect of Vākpāla (younger brother of Dharmapāla) in the Pāla c.ps starting from the Bhagalpur c.p. of Nārāyaṇapāla. In our inscription, the two virtues, 'naya' and 'vikrama' have been attributed to Devapāla, but in a somewhat different form. Instead of 'naya', the feminine term 'nīti' has been used; similarly, the masculine term 'vikrama' has been made feminine 'vikramā' on the analogy of 'nīti', and the two terms are taken to be two females but nevertheless, meaning two virtues, of Devapāla.⁸

In the second caraṇa of verse 6, the composer has hinted in a figurative way that king Devapāla turned the wide earth into the yard of his own house (bhavan=āṅgana)

In the following verse (V. 7) Devapāla has been given the appellation 'mahā-samara-nātaka-sūtradhāraḥ' (V. 7) literally, 'stage director of the drama of great wars', apparently in recognition of his successful leadership in many great wars. With the golds (i.e. wealth) collected from expeditions, he built a temple of Sugata (Sugata-sadma) and an abode of Gaurī (grihañ=ca Gauryā(h) which was an object of curiosity (kautukañ=ca) and an ornament in the forehead (tilakañ=ca) of the three worlds (jagat=traye'pi). The reading of 'Śauryā' (for Gauryā) by SCM is wrong for 'ga' and 'śa' are written distinctly in this inscription. The building (together?) of a temple of Sugata and an abode of Gaurī shows the non-sectarian attitude of Devapāla. Unfortunately, no trace of this unique piece of architecture has survived for us. We do not even know where it was situated.⁹

In verse 8 the composer has depicted a scene of the battle-field in which the enemies along with their war elephants were annihilated. It is told that Devapāla collected tributes from kings of the entire world.

The enemies who fought him had no hope of success against Devapāla in battle; but by sacrificing their lives in the battlefield they hoped to obtain fame, to gain access to heaven, and enjoy the company of the celestial damsels there. (Verse 9).

In verse 10 Devapāla is compared to lord Śive. In concrete terms, Devapāla is given the credit of conquering Kāmarūpa (Assam) at ease, which was his first achievement, and of extracting covetable tributes from inaccessible regions of the Himalayas.¹⁰ He demonstrated perfection of self and supreme divinity like the unsurpassed god Śiva.

R&I have wrongly read 'huta-Kāmarūpaṃ' (for hṛita-Kāmarūpaṃ) and in this they have been followed by SCM. Devapāla's contemporary king of Kāmarūpa could have been Prālabha, Harjaravarman (c. 815-32 A.D.), or the latter's son Vanamālavarman (c. 832-55 A.D.)¹¹.

As for the Himalayan campaigns, it may be mentioned that the Mirzapur c.p. describes Devapāla as 'Nepāla-nātha-vijayī'.

Māhaṭā-the queen of Devapāla: V. 11.

Verse 11 informs us that Devapāla married Māhaṭā, the much accomplished daughter of king Durlabharāja of the lineage of the Cāhamānas. The name Māhaṭā, daughter of Durlabharāja was already known from the Mirzapur c.p., where, however, no mention was made of her lineage. In the Mirzapur c.p. also Māhaṭā's admirable qualities have been lavishly extolled.

Durlabharāja of our inscription has been identified by R&I with Durlabharāja I of the Cāhamāna dynasty of Śākambharī (son of Gopendraka and father of Guvāka I) who flourished in the eighth century A.D. and whose exploits are traced to a late work called *Prithvīrāja-vijaya*. In their view the allegiance of the Cāhamānas wavered between the Pratīhāras and the Pālas according to the demands of the situation.¹² The Pāla-Cāhamāna matrimonial relation was re-established later when Śūrapāla I married a Cāhamāna princess.¹³

King Mahendrapāla : Verses 12-16

Verses 12 to 16 are devoted to Mahendrapāla, during whose reign this c.p. ins. was issued.

Verse 12 compares Mahendrapāla to Viṣṇu. Like Viṣṇu (=Kṛiṣṇa) he was born of the Devakī-like mother, Māhaṭā; was adored by thousands of men and divinities; bore the burden of the earth with ease (as Viṣṇu did in his

boar incarnation); was chosen by fortune (Lakṣmī) as lord on her own accord; was a divinity (deva) and the most perfect man (puruṣottama).

In verse 13 the composer poet has given his imagination a free run. The thick dust kicked up by Mahendrapāla's army that set out on a conquest of the regions (āśā-vijaya-prayāṇe) went upwards and remained suspended there filling the entire sky, creating the illusion of a solid earth up there, but on coming to learn that it was not so, the confused (flying) groups of Vidyādhara attributed this unusual phenomenon to some astonishing trick. Such aerial flights of imagination on the part of the composers are not uncommon in Pāla c.p.s. Scholars have any way failed to translate this verse correctly. The misreading of 'ūrvvī-drume' for 'urvvī-bhrame' has landed Ramesh and Iyer in a queer situation (op. cit., p. 20 and foot note 2; Translation, p. 25. Cf. also 'aśvā-vijayapathān' by SCM).

In a figurative way, verse 14 claims for Mahendrapāla the overlordship of the whole country (i.e. India. From the Himalayas (ā-prāleya-gireḥ) in the north to the sea (separating Srīlankā from India) the water of which had been stirred up by the arrows of Rāma, the enemy of Rāvaṇa, and from the eastern to the western mountains, i.e. the Eastern and the Western Ghats, which adorn the faces of the two directions—kings bowed down before Mahendrapāla treating him as their overlord. This conforms to the stereotyped concept of a pan-Indian empire (Cakravartī-kṣetra)¹⁴ and echoes claims made for Devapāla in his Munger and Nalanda c.p.s.¹⁵, -V. 15.

In the absence of any supporting evidence, the claim cannot be taken in its face value in the case of Mahendrapāla. Wrongly read words in this verse include 'Vṛiṣabha-khaṇḍākhyā', 'ā-Lohita', 'adhityakāt' and 'dūrānantarair'—see Check Lists).

In verse 15 the composer has shown his poetical imagination while trying to point out the spread of Mahendrapāla's prowess in different directions, even across the seas.

Verse 16 seems to imply that Mahendrapāla was not inclined to pursue a vigorous aggressive policy towards his enemies. The key to this interpretation is the word 'vyājaghnire' (from vhan, meaning 'killed', 'destroyed' etc.), which has been wrongly read as 'vyājṛimbhire' by R&I and translated as 'increased'. This has reference to the fate of his 'enjoyment of the war-games'.

Success of Mahendrapāla

Though his c.p. does not refer to any specific conquest to Mahendrapāla's credit, it can be safely assumed that he succeeded in maintaining intact the power base of the Pālas in north Bengal and Bihar as would appear from the discovery

of numerous stone inscriptions ranging in dates from year 2 to 15 of king Mahendrapāla from this region¹⁶. The discovery of the present c.p. has overnight changed the earlier perception that the Mahendrapāla of these inscriptions was Mahendrapāla I (c. 883-908 A.D.) of the Gurjara Pratihāra dynasty.

Prose Portion: Lines 25-20, divided into six Sections, A to F

Now begins the prose portion which has been divided by us into the following six sections for convenience of reference and better understanding of the subject matter.

Sections:

- A. Lines 25-30 Sa khalu Bhāgīrathī-patha ... Mahendrapāladevaḥ kuśalī
- B. Lines 30-35. Śrī-Puṇḍravarddhana-bhuktau....Ṭaṅgil=ārdha-ś(s) roto(')vadhīh
- C. Lines 35-39. Evan=niyamita-sīmni....sam=ādiśati ca
- D. Lines 39-44. (Matam=astu bhavatām Śrīmad=Bhattāraka-pādā dadatv=iti)
- E. Lines 44-47. Ato='smābhis=tadīya vijñāptyā tath=aiva pradattaḥ
- F. Lines 47-50. Yatā(o) bhavadbhiḥ sarvvair=eva...dharmm=ānusan-sana (samśinaḥ) ślokāḥ

The main points of interest may now be discussed under the different sections as outlined above.

Section A: The reigning king and the grandeur of the Jayaskandhāvāra Lines 25-30 (sa khalu ... Mahendrapāladevaḥ kuśalī)

The grant was issued by Parama-Saugata Paramabhattāraka Mahārājādhirāja Śrī-Mahendrapāladeva, who meditated on the feet (pād=ānudhyāta) of Parama-Saugata Parameśvara Paramabhattāraka Mahārājādhirāja Śrī-Devapāladeva, being in good health (kuśalī), from the victorious camp pitched at Kuddāla-khātaka (wrongly read as Auddālakhātaka by R&I). This stock set of phraseology is used to describe the might and grandeur of all the Pāla jayaskandhāvāras.

In view of the mention of so many jayaskandhāvāras in the Pāla c.ps it would appear that some of the 'camps of victory' were make-shift arrangements for the temporary residence of the king during his visit on special occasions, whereas the ones at Pātalīputra, Mudgagiri, Rāmavati etc. big cities were built on a permanent basis.

Section B: Location and Boundaries of Nandadīrghikā udraṅga

Lines 30-35 (Śrī-Puṇḍravarddhana-bhuktau ... Ṭaṅgil-ārdha-ś(s)roto(') vadhīh)

The boundaries of the donated land at Nandadīrghikā udraṅga comprised in the Kuddālakhātaka (wrongly read as 'Kundalakhāta by R&I) viṣaya under the Puṇḍravarddhana-bhukti are given next. It deserves to be mentioned here that the donated land in the jajilpara c.p. or Gopala III¹⁷ is located in Kuddālakhāta viṣaya comprised in the Puṇḍravarddhana bhukti. It is quite likely that Kuddālakhātaka and Kuddālakhāta refer to the same viṣaya. The Jajilpara c.p. was, however, issued from a jayaskandhāvāra named Vaṭaparvatikā. In view of both the inscriptions coming from the Malda district (which also claims the Khalimpur c.p.), it would not be unreasonable to hold that Kuddālakhātaka/khāta viṣaya as also the jayaskandhāvāra of Kuddālakhātaka were situated in about the same region. The term Kuddālakhāta/khātaka (literally, dug with spades) bears an association of the development of land with spades, but there is no knowing when such activity was undertaken in a significant scale that gave its name to the viṣaya / jayaskandhāvāra.

The eastern, western, northern and southern boundaries of Nanda-dīrghikā-udraṅga have been demarcated with reference to such landmarks as stream (srotikā), or arddha-srotikā (half-stream) of rivers, embankments (bandha/ bandhāka), fountain or spring (nirjjhara), water reservoir of sorts (ādhāra), water-holes (kuṇḍā), raised footway (āli-for demarcation between lands), low land (avakhāta), termite mound (valmīka stūpa), aśvattha, vilva and āmalakī trees, and the like. The recurrence of the river Ṭaṅgila seems to suggest that it was a dominant feature of the landscape of the locality. Ramesh and Iyer have suggested the identification of some names in connection with the demarcation of boundaries (e.g. Ṭaṅgila, Kubja-ghaṭikā, Nārāyaṇavāsa, Kāsiggada etc.) with the help of modern maps and village list.¹⁸ Nothing definite can be said on these except for Ṭaṅgila (=the river Tangan).

The names 'Golaṭi', Jāgaravāsaka' and Ṣaṇḍāla (correct reading: ṣaṇ=ṇāla) have been wrongly read by them.¹⁹ The word 'ṣaṇ=ṇal=āntarita' (six nalas apart) may suggest the continuation of measurement by 'nala' as a unit. The picture that emerges in one's mind of the Nandadīrghikā udraṅga is not of a congested area or a hub throbbing with town-life or commercial activities (udraṅga), but rather of a rural type of locality amidst natural surroundings with sufficient vacant space and natural objects around, which is why it is difficult to be certain about the correct meaning of the term 'udraṅga' as

mentioned here. Is it a town, or a tax/toll collection centre, or is it something else?

Section C: List of Dignitaries and Other Addressees

Lines 35-39 (Evan=niyamita-sīmni....sam=ādīśati ca)

This section (lines 35-40) gives a stereotyped list of the royal officials/servants (rāja-pād=opajīvinah) of different designations and categories who are supposed to have been present within the specified boundary (evan=niyamita-sīmni) of the donated land to hear the king's order. The officials enlisted here are : (1) rājanaka, (2) rājaputra, (3) kumārāmātya, (4) bhuktipati, (5) viṣayapati, (6) senāpati, (7) uparika, (8) tadāyuktaka, (9) viniyuktaka, (10) daṇḍika, (11) daṇḍapāśika, (12) caur=oddharaṇika, (13) dauṣṣādhyasādhanika, (14) khola, (15) dūta, (16) gamāgamika, (17) abhitvaramāṇa, (18) hasty=aśva-nau-balavyāpṛitaka, (19) go-mahiṣy=ajāvīkā-vaḍav=ādhyakṣa and others subsisting on the king's feet, as well as those falling under the categories of cātas, bhaṭas, the district officers (viṣaya-vyavahāriṇah) including the karaṇas (sa-karaṇān) as may be present from time to time (yathākāl=ādhyāsi) and the resident cultivators / or residents and cultivators (pratīvāsinaḥ kṣetrakarāmś=ca). The present list is not among the largest available in Pāla copper plates. Khola which is of uncertain meaning, finds mention in the Khalimpur c.p. Reference to 'viṣaya-vyavahāriṇah sakaraṇān' is also not so common in Pāla c.ps. The assemblage of all the functionaries (and others involved) in the site of the land to be donated appears to be more notional than real. To all these, especially honouring the brāhmaṇas (this part is commonly more elaborate in other Pāla c.ps), the king (Mahendrapāla) pays due respect, makes known and issues these commands :

Section D: Purport of the Grant for which Vajradeva approaches the king

Lines 39-44 (Matam=astu bhavatām ... Śrīmad=Bhaṭṭarakapādā dadatv=iti)

This Section deals with the very important question of what this grant is all about. Prior to introducing the matter squarely, the king wishes the consent of those who (are supposed to) have assembled at the donation site of Nandadīrghikā udraṅga (boundaries of Nandadīrghikā udraṅga and the list of the addressees have been provided in Sections B and C above).

Then the matter is introduced by the king, speaking in the 1st Person (pl.) as follows : 'We have been informed by Mahāsenāpati (the great Commander of the army), Śrī-Vajradeva, through the mouth of the dūtaka (Mahāsenāpati Śrī-Vajradevana dūtakamukhena vayam=vijñāpitāḥ).'

This is followed by Vajradeva's version in which Vajradeva speaks in the 1st Person (Sing.) and the king figures in the 3rd Person (Pl.) and which is put to the king through the mouth of the dūtaka in the following manner: 'I have caused a vihāra (Buddhist monastery) to be constructed in Nandadīrghikā udraṅga (Nandadīrghik=odraṅge mayā vihāraḥ kāritaḥ) for the enhancement of the religious merit of my mother and father, myself and the whole multitude of living beings. May his Gracious Majesty (literally, the feet of his Gracious Majesty - 'Bhaṭṭarakapādā(=ḥ) grant (dadatu) the Nandadīrghikā udraṅga as' written above for worship (pūjana), writing/copying (of Buddhist religious texts - 'lekhana'), etc.; garments (for monks- 'cīvara'), food/alms (for monks - 'piṇḍapāta'), beds (śayana), seats (āsana), requisities for the sick (glāna-pratyaya), medicines (bhaiṣajya), other requisites (for monks - 'parīṣkāra), etc. (ādy=artham); for repair of damages and cracks (of the vihāra-'khaṇḍa-sphuṭita-samādhān=ārtham') - as fit/applicable (yath=ārham), - of the divine lord Buddha (Bhagavato Buddha-bhaṭṭarakasya); the place (abode) of Prajñāpāramitā and all the other female religious leaders/divinities (Prajñāpāramit=ādī-sakala-dharmma-nettrī-sthānasya); the group of Bodhisatvas of the noble Avaivarttika order (āry=Āvaivarttika-Bodhisatva-gaṇasya); the noble congregation of monks adhering to the individual eight holy personages (aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgala-ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya); as also for the unblemished enjoyment (anavadya-bhog=ārtham) with the apportionment (of facilities / land) made according to my plan (mat-parikalpita-vibhāgena), also of others of my choice (anyeṣām=api mam=ābhimatānām).'

This important Section has been the subject of lots of misreading, wrong interpretation and wrong translation at the hands of scholars.²⁰

The most blatant of these are : - (1) wrongly taking king Mahendrapāla (and not Vajradeva) as the builder of the Nandadīrghikā udraṅga, and (2) wrongly taking Vajradeva as the dūtaka of this grant. G. Bhattacharya (GB) correctly pinpoints the fallacies of R&I as well as BNM and observes: 'unfortunately MUKHERJEE himself has become a victim of the blunder(s) of both the authors.'²¹ Strangely enough B. N. Mukherjee makes repeated assertions about king Mahendrapāla's being the founder of the monastery (vihāra) while revealing information about a t. c. seal impression found at the site of the monastery which speaks (according to his own reading) 'of the noble congregation of monks of the H(N) am(dī)rghi-vihāra, caused (to be founded) by the illustrious Vajradeva'²² In addition to this, he blindly follows the readings of R&I and shares with them the errors with regard to the following words: Nandadīrghik=odraṅgo (for Nanadīrghik=odraṅgam),

lekha(pa) n=ādy= arthe (for lekhan=ādy=artham), samādhān= ādy=artham (for samādhān= ārtham)²³.

Among other instances of misreadings by scholars mention may be made of 'mahā vihāraḥ' (for 'mayā vihāraḥ' by KKG, SCM-1 and ACS) and 'puj= ānala-khādy=ānn=ādy=artham' (for 'pūjana-lekhanādy=artham' by KKG.²⁴ There is no reference to dedication of the vihāra for proper enjoyment, at the feet of Bhaṭṭāraka (Buddha) as KKG construes. The split of the land into 'amśas' as indicated by SCM or KKG is likewise not supported by the original text. Like many of his fanciful assertions, SCM's statement about a three-fold division of the donated land²⁵ is a figment of his own imagination.

Avaivarttika and hierarchy of Buddhist personages

The appearance of the term 'Avaivarttika' in this inscription deserves attention. A community of Buddhist monks affiliated to this order of the Mahāyāna school (Māhāyānik=Avaivarttika-bhikṣu-saṅgha) was already known to us from the Gunaighar (Comilla district, now Bangladesh) c.p. grant of Vainyagupta, dated G.E. 188 (=A.D. 507-08). To Ramesh and Iyer goes the credit of correctly reading the term 'Avaivarttika' in lines 38-39 of the Nalanda c.p. of Devapāla.²⁶ Formerly, the letters for 'āry=Āvaivarttika were read as 'āyārthe tānitra (tri)ka' by H. Shastri, and as 'ārcārthe tā (ta)traka' by N.G. Majumdar, who interpreted the portion in their own ways.²⁷ Ramesh and Iyer have also correctly pointed out the significance of the term 'Avaivarttika' as 'firmly set on the road to enlightenment'.²⁸ B. N. Mukherjee has further elaborated on the concept with reference to some Buddhist texts.²⁹

It appears that Vajradeva was an adherent of this order and founded the vihāra as a centre for monks subscribing to its tenets.

Services and Recipients Juxtaposed

On scrutiny of the lines in this Section it is possible to observe that some services were intended for some recipients. It may further be noticed that service of each category ends with 'artham' or 'ādy=artham' (for such purposes) whereas recipient of each category has a genitive case-ending. As it is the list of recipients does not fully answer to the list of services, and who is to get what has not been specifically spelt out. In fact the term 'yath=ārtham' seems to leave the decision to our discretion. The following is an attempt on our part to juxtapose the recipients against the Services.

Table 1 : Jagjibanpur c.p. of Mahendrapāla

A.	B.
Services offered	Recipients of Services
No.	No.
i) (a) pūjana-(b) lekhanā etc. (ādy=artham)	1. Bhagavato Budha-bhaṭṭārakasya
ii) (a) cīvara-(b) piṇḍapāta- (c) śayana-(d) āsana- (e) glāna-pratyaya-(f) bhaisajya- (g) pariṣkāra etc. (pariṣkāra=ādy=artham)	2. Prajñāpāramit=ādi-sakala-dharm-nettrī-sthānasya
iii) khaṇḍa-sphuṭita-samādhāna (samādhān=ārtham)	3. āry=Āvaivarttika-Bodhisatva-gaṇasya
iv) mat-parikalpita-vibhāgen= ānavadya-bhoga (bhoga=ārtham)	4. aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgala-ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya
	5*. Not mentioned, but apparently the structures of the vihāra.
	6. anyeṣām=api mam=ābhimatānām

In our view, Recipients of Service No. (i) both (a) and (b) are those enlisted under Nos. 1, 2 and 3, i.e. the ones who are objects of reverence, but are not living. Services enlisted under No. (ii) - from (a) to (g) are to be extended to living persons. monks belonging to the bhikṣu saṅgha=Recipients 4; Services under (iii) can only be meant for Recipient 5.* Services listed under (iv) are specifically designed for Recipients 6. The whole inter-relation between Services and Recipients is summed up in the following equation:

Table 1(a) : Equation of Services and Recipients - Jagjibanpur c.p.

A	B
(i)	= 1, 2, 3
(ii)	= 4
(iii)	= 5*
(iv)	= 6

Parallels from the Nalanda, C.P. of Devapāla³⁰

Besides 'āry=Āvaivarttika Bodhisatva-gaṇasya', our inscription shares with the Nalanda c.p. many other expressions in respect of Section D. Services and Recipients may likewise be discerned in the Nalanda c.p. and these may be arranged in the following order :-

Table 2: Nalanda c.p. of Devapāla

A	B
Services offered	Recipients of Services
(i) (a) bali-(b) caru-(c) satra-(d) cīvara-(e) piṇḍapāta-(f) śayana-(g) āsana-(h) glāna-pratyaya-(i) bheṣajya-(ādy=artham)	1. Bhagavato Buddha-bhaṭṭāarakasya
(ii) lekhaṇa-(ādy=artham)	2. Prajñāpāramit=ādi-sakala-dharmmanetrī-sthānasya
(iii) khaṇḍa-spuṭita-samādhān=artham	3. ārya-Āvaivarttika-Bodhisatva-gaṇasya
	4. aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgalasya
	5. cātur=diś=ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya
	6. dharmmaratnasya
	7. vihārasya

Both H. Shastri and N. G. Majumdar have clubbed 1 and 2 together, taking 2 as adjective to 1. H. Shastri translates the whole (i.e. 1 and 2 combined) as 'the blessed lord Buddha, the abode of all the leading virtues like the Prajñāpāramitā'.³¹ 'N. G. Majumdar translates the same as 'of the lord Buddha-bhaṭṭārika, who is the eye of all the virtues including Prajñāpāramitā', deriving 'netrī' from 'netra' (eye)³². But in our view, 1 and 2 may be treated as separate entities and netrīsthānasya may be taken to mean netrīsthānīyasya. According to Majumdar, 'The expression aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgalasya is here in apposition to cāturdiś=ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya which follows, and the two expressions taken together would mean 'the community of monks from four quarters comprising the eight great classes of intelligent beings'.³³ In our view, the genitive case-ending in 'aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgalasya' suggests that it is a separate entity. But in the Jagjibanpur c.p. 'aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgal=ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya' has been knit together in a compound (samāsa) to indicate a single entity. N. G. Majumdar has explained the significance of the expression aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgala' on the basis of Buddhist philosophy and he has equated 'aṣṭa-ārya-pudgala' with 'aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgala' which again he has translated as 'the eight great classes of intelligent beings'. In the Nalanda c.p. Service Nos. (ii) and (iii) are specifically earmarked for Recipient Nos. 6 and 7 respectively. 'Dharmmaratna' here seems to stand for Buddhist religious texts. Services listed under (i) were apparently extended to Recipient Nos. 1 to 5, as applicable.

To come back to our inscription and with the hindsight of the Nalanda c.p. just discussed, it appears more practicable to take 'aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa-pudgala' in the sense as suggested by N.G. Majumdar than to take it in the sense of the 'eight spiritual stages (bhūmis)' crossed by the Avaivarttika (=avivarttanaśīla)

Bodhisatvas as proposed by B. N. Mukherjee,³⁴ for the term 'aṣṭa-mahāpuruṣa' rather indicates that the number of the 'mahāpuruṣas' was eight.

Similar arrangements in the Bhagalpur c.p. of Nārāyaṇapāla³⁵

We have just noticed the many similarities that the Jagjibanpur c.p. shares with the Nalanda c.p. of Devapāla while detailing the purport of the grant. As both of these inscriptions dwell on the construction and religious activities of two Buddhist vihāras, such similarities between them cannot be said to be altogether unexpected. But there is occasion for surprise when we see important similarities of the Jagjibanpur c.p. with the Bhagalpur c.p. of Nārāyaṇapāla at this juncture. For the Bhagalpur c.p. is concerned not with a Buddhist vihāra, but with a temple complex meant for lord Śiva and the congregation of Pāśupata teachers. The Services offered in that inscription and the recipients of such services may now be noticed.

Table 3 : Bhagalpur c.p. of Nārāyaṇapāla

A	B
Services offered	Recipients of Services
i) (a) pūjā- (b) bali- (c) caru- (d) sattrā - (e) nava-karma etc. (nava-karmādy=artham)	1. Bhagavataḥ Śiva-bhaṭṭāarakasya
ii) (a) śayan-(b) āsana-(c) glāna-pratyaya-(d) bhaiṣajya-(e) pariṣkāra etc. (pariṣkāra=ādy=artham)	2. Pāśupata-ācārya-parśadaś=ca
iii) sva-parikalpita-vibhāgena anavadya-bhog=artham	3. anyeṣām=api sv=ābhimatānām

A comparison of Table 3 with Table 1 (Jagjibanpur c.p.) would show remarkable similarities: Services (ii) and (iii) in Table 3 are identical with (ii) and (iv) of Table 1 except that the latter has two additional items (cīvara and piṇḍapāta) which are missing in Table 3, and Table 3 reads 'sva-parikalpita' (iii) instead of 'mat-parikalpita' (iv) of Table 1. 'Pūjana' in Table 1 (i-a) has the form 'pūjā' (i-a) in Table 3. As for Recipients, 6 of Table 1 is 3 of Table 3. Nos. 1 and 2 of Table 3 may be likened to 1 (Bhagavato Buddha-bhaṭṭāarakasya) and 4 (ārya-bhikṣu-saṅghasya) of Table 1.

The similarities in approach of the Śaivite temple with a Buddhist vihāra will be easier to understand if we remember that the Śaivite temple complex was caused to be constructed by Nārāyaṇapāla himself who was also responsible for devising the activities to be conducted there. In spite of his

personal Śaivite leanings, the traditional Pāla attachment to Buddhism is betrayed by the appearance of some typical Buddhist terms (as listed under Services, No. ii-a to e), though not all, in its vocabulary.

Similar arrangements in the Gunaighar c.p. of Vainyagupta³⁶

We may end our quest for epigraphic parallels by having a closer look at a much earlier inscription - the Gunaighar c.p. of Vainyagupta of Gupta Year 188 (A.D. 507-08). The following Table shows the Service-Recipient equation as provided by this c.p.

Table 4 : Service-Recipient equation in the Gunaighar c.p.

A	B
Services offered	Recipients of Services
i) gandha-puṣpa-dīpa-dhūp=ādi pravarttana (pravarttanāya)	1. Bhagavato Buddhasya
ii) (a) cīvara-(b) piṇḍapāta-(c) śayana-(d) āsana-(e) glāna-pratyaya-(f) bhaisajya=ādi paribhoga (paribhogāya)	2. (tasya ca) bhikṣu-saṅghasya
iii) khaṇḍa-phuṭṭa-pratisaṃskāra-karaṇa (karaṇāya)	3. vihāre ca

The Service-Recipient equation has been clearly spelt out in the Gunaighar c.p., which should help us solve this aspect of the Jagjibanpur c.p. in respect of the terms which are common in both the inscriptions (cf. Tables 1 and 4).

Some typically Buddhist terms in the services offered

The Services offered in the Jagjibanpur c.p. (see Table 1, iia to iig) are related to the discipline followed by Buddhist monks from much earlier times.

'Cīvara' means the dress or robe of a Buddhist monk. Generally, it consisted of three parts (ticīvaram). 'Piṇḍapāta' has reference to the food received in the alms bowl of a Buddhist monk. 'Śayan=āsana' (Pāli senāsanam) seems to have meant originally 'sleeping and sitting' and hence 'dwelling'. Generally it is translated as beds and seats, which is followed by us. 'Glāna-pratyaya' (Pāli gilānapaccayo) indicates the medical requisites for the sick (from glāna √glai). 'Bhaisajya' means medicine (bhīṣaj=a physician). 'Parīṣkāra' (Pāli parikkhāro) stands for the (other) requisites of a Buddhist monk (cf. attha parikkhāra-the eight requisites of the Buddhist Priest.³⁷)

Correction of some mis-interpretations

In the light of the data of the four representative c.ps as well as usage,

it would appear that B.N. Mukherjee's translation of the expression 'glāna-pratyaya-bhaisajya-parīṣkāra=ady=artham khaṇḍa-sphuṭita-samādhān=ādy=artham' (sic) as 'purification [after illness?] etc. and for fragmented (or) fully blown (i.e. deep) religious meditation etc.'³⁸ is ingenious but misplaced. The correct meanings of the terms in 'glāna-pratyaya-bhaisajya-parīṣkāra= ādy=artham' have been discussed above. 'Khaṇḍa-sphuṭita-samādhān=artham' has nothing to do with meditation, but is concerned with the upkeep of the (buildings of) the vihāra (cf. Tables 2 and 4 for confirmation). The fallacy of B. N. Mukherjee's view as reflected in his translation : 'and also for others of my (i.e. the king's) choice and by the division settled by me for the faultless enjoyment (by the beneficiaries) the king gives thus (i.e. the following manner)³⁹—attributing Vajradeva's credit to the king – has been already pointed out. In this, however, Mukherjee is not alone.⁴⁰

Section E: King's approval of the grant with rights and privileges Lines 44-47 (Ato='smābhis=tadiya vijñāptyā tath=aiva pradattaḥ)

The grant of the request along with the customary rights and privileges with the tenure of the land has been outlined in this Section.

Some scholars have failed to comprehend the king's approval part (recorded in the 1st person as 'asmābhiḥ...tath=aiva pradattaḥ') correctly which has resulted in erroneous and cumbersome interpretation and translation (cf. for example, R&I's Translation: 'I gave as if directly by myself (bhāṭṭārakapāda)', which has been closely followed by SCM.).

The Nandadīrghikā udraṅga was granted with land attached thereto within the specified four boundaries (sva-sambaddha-bhūmi-sametaś=catus=sīmā-paryantaḥ). The rights and privileges to be enjoyed by the donee are indicated by the expressions : (1) satalaḥ, (2) soddeśaḥ, (3) soparikaraḥ, (4) saghaṭṭa-taropetaḥ (5) sadaśāpacāraḥ, (6) sacauroddharaṇaḥ, (7) pariḥṛita-sarvvapīḍaḥ, (8) a-cāta-bhaṭa-praveśaḥ, (9) a-kiñcit-pragrāhyaḥ, and (10) rājakuḷ=ābhāvya-sarvva-pratyāya-sametaḥ. The land was granted according to the 'bhūmicchidra-nyāya', and was made tenable for the duration of the moon, the sun and the earth (i.e. for all time to come). The rights and privileges handed over with the land to the donee follow the general pattern of Pāla land charters.

Though not specifically mentioned in the inscription, it may be assumed that Mahāsenāpati Vajradeva, who had caused the vihāra to be built at Nandadīrghikā udraṅga was the original donor of the land of the udraṅga. He apparently approached the king to grant it tax-free status according to the bhūmicchidra-nyāya along with all the rights and privileges that went with it, by duly recording it in a copper plate charter. Apparently Vajradeva made

payments to the state as compensation for the loss of revenue it would entail to the treasury, and to make sure that he obtained the religious merit for the donation.⁴¹ However, such details are generally not recorded in the Pāla charters and the present grant is no exception.

In the present case the vihāra was the donee, i.e. the beneficiary of the donation, and to start with, Vajradeva appears to have played an important part in the administration of the vihāra, doubling both as the donor and the donee.

Section F : Solicitation of Approval and Cooperation of all, Date Lines 47-50 (Yatā(o) bhavadbhiḥ sarvvair=eva ... dharmm=ānuśansana (śamsinaḥ) ślokāḥ

This Section (lines 47-50) follows the customary pattern of Pāla c.ps in which the approval of all for the grant and the co-operation of future kings for its continuance are solicited. The resident cultivators (or residents and cultivators - 'prativāsibhiḥ kṣetrakaraaiś=ca') were to make over (to the donee) the customary taxes, payments in kind and other types of revenues.

Date of the grant : line 50

The grant was dated in the year 7 (of Mahendrapāla), in the Vaiśākha day 2. B. N. Mukherjee has mentioned the date as the 7th day of Mahendrapāla's regnal year, which is wrong.

Second phase of verses : 17-34 (lines 50-72).

Customary benedictory Verses : Verses 17-20.

A few customary benedictory verses extolling the merits of making and protecting a gift and the demerits of its misappropriation now follow. These are the only four verses the present inscription has in common with other Pāla copper plate inscriptions.

Dūtaka of the grant = Śūrapāla - V. 21.

In this meritorious act (sukṛita-karṇaṇi, viz. issue of the land grant) Śūrapāla has been made the dūtaka (emissary) by Śrīmat-Saṅgrāmatāra, i.e. the Star/Saviour in wars (an appellation used to designate the king Mahendrapāla), like Saumitri (i.e. Lakṣmaṇa) had been by Rāma. This Śūrapāla, son of Devapāla by Māhaṭā (daughter of Durlabharāja) was already known to us from his Mirzapur c.p.⁴² The present inscription shows that Śūrapāla was preceded on the throne by his co-uterine elder brother Mahendrapāla. There is, however, no mention of Mahendrapāla in Śūrapāla's copper plate. Whether this omission stems from the preference for recording only the direct line of succession, or there is more to it than that, cannot be said at the present state of our knowledge.

Some scholars have erred in thinking that Mahāsenāpati Vajradeva was a/the dūtaka (messenger) of the grant apparently because of their failure to grasp the correct meaning of the expression 'Śrī-Vajradevena dūtaka-mukhena'. This is rather the standard format in Pāla c.ps. while recording large donations for religious institutions in which the king was apparently approached through an influential intermediary even at the initial stage. This intermediary gained royal recognition as the dūtaka of the grant.⁴³

Once assuming that Vajradeva was the dūtaka of this grant, when faced with the king's younger brother Śūrapāla (I) being mentioned as the dūtaka (line 54) R&I decide that 'this charter is unique in having two royal messengers (dūtaka)'.⁴⁴ KKG also falls a victim of this confusion⁴⁵, while SCM is somewhat guarded by his meaningless translation.⁴⁶ So far as B.N. Mukherjee is concerned, he has no knowledge that Śūrapāla is mentioned as the dūtaka of this grant. For him Vajradeva is the only dūtaka.⁴⁷

Mahāsenāpati Śrī-Vajradeva and his predecessors : verses 22-34 (lines 54-72)

What gives the present inscription a speciality is the detailed eulogy in 14 verses of the donor Mahāsenāpati Vajradeva, his father Nārāyaṇadeva and grandfather Devaradeva which almost rivals in scale the eulogy of the Pāla kings.

Devaradeva, the grandfather of Vajradeva : Verses 22-23

Born in a great family (kule mahati), Devaradeva possessed an enviable reputation, and his fame was sung across the world. Even to-day, his praises are the first things sung by the eminent people while talking about virtues. -V. 22.

He was noted for his possession, in extraordinary abundance, of the three virtues of sacrifice, truthfulness and valour. -V. 23.

From the vague praises applied to Devaradeva it appears that he had no specific achievement to his credit and it was his son Nārāyaṇadeva who was the real founder of the fortunes of the family.

Nārāyaṇadeva, son of Devaradeva : Verses 24-27.

Verses 24-27 are devoted to Devaradeva's son Nārāyaṇadeva. A profusion of praises is showered on him to the effect that he combined in him great military and physical power, pleasing appearance as well as remarkable attributes of head and heart.

Verse 24 states that he was an abode of Kamalā (i.e. Lakṣmī or Fortune).⁴⁸ He was a lover of righteousness and held truth as dear as his life. He possessed (great) physical strength and was highly esteemed by his teacher (guruṇā mahīyān).

V. 25 mentions the killing by him with his sword with great bloodshed the enemies and their mighty elephants for which his fame spread widely.

V. 26 praises him for the more subtle or sublime aspects of his character and personality. The composer has also taken the opportunity to project his own skill while focusing the qualities of his subject (see Translation for details). There is no way of knowing how far this panegyric reflects the reality. But it can be safely assumed that he was the real founder of the fortunes of his family.

The shower of praises on Nārāyaṇadeva continues unabated in verse 27. At the end of the stanza we are told that the illustrious king Dharmapāla made him chief (governor) of the maṇḍala of Darddaraṇḍī (Śrī-Dharmapālo nṛipatir= adhipatim=maṇḍale Darddaraṇḍyām). R&I read the name of the maṇḍala as Darddarānya and G. Bhattacharya, as Darddaraṇī (New Pāla Ruler named Mahendrapāla, p. 170). Strangely enough, according to the interpretation of KKG and ACS it was Nārāyaṇadeva who made Dharmapāla the ruler of Darddaraṇḍī! The use of the 'prathamā vibhakti' with Dharmapāla militates against this. Note also the use of the 'dviṭīyā vibhakti' in 'adhipatim'. The location of the maṇḍala (not mentioned anywhere else) is not known. The present verse also makes grandiloquent claims (e.g. he was like fire unto the enemy faggots and rubbed his white lotus-like feet against hundreds of crowns which had been taken from them; he was the protector of the established social order; and he was the sole lord of the earth) which do not appear consistent with his subordinate status.⁴⁹

Verse 27 also allows us a glimpse of the tender side of his character. We are told that to the beloved ones he was as the sun is to lotuses, and that he turned self-effacing in the face of praises of his well-reputed qualities. The second of these traits reminds one of such bashfulness on the part of Dharmapāla on hearing his own praises.⁵⁰

Kalyāṇadevī, wife of Nārāyaṇadeva : Verses 28-29

Verses 28 and 29 lavishly glorify Kalyāṇadevī, the wife of Nārāyaṇadeva.

Rightly named Kalyāṇadevī, she carried the three worlds (in herself) and constituted the distinctive mark on the forehead thereof. In her the three vargas (divisions of human activities) reached their fulfilment. -V. 28

She did not seem to be an ordinary mortal person of this earth. The people who were spell-bound by her extraordinary charm and grace debated amongst themselves about her true identity in a way that reminds us of the manner queen Raṇḍadevī has been eulogised⁵¹ in the Nalanda and Munger c.ps of Devapāla. -V. 29.

Vajradeva—son of Nārāyaṇadeva and Kalyāṇadevī : Verses 30-34

On her (Kalyāṇadevī, who was like the sky) was begotten by him (Nārāyaṇadeva), who was like the sun, a son, the illustrious Vajradeva, the abode of perfection made by the creator. Valiant, single-minded in doing good to (all) living beings (satv=opakar=aika-rataḥ-this may show his Buddhist credential), he possesses an unblemished nature. - Verse 30.

Verse 31 lauds Vajradeva's warlike qualities and attainments. He gained possession of his beloved Lakṣmī (Lakṣmīn=kulajām dadhat-praṇayinīm) with the rise of his power (vīry=odayāt). The battlefield was flooded with the blood of the great tuskers he brought down by his sword. He reached celebrity in the world by marrying the rarely attainable Vijaya-Śrī in battle (durllabhām saṅgrāme Vijaya-Śriyam pariṇayan) in which the enemies were offered as oblation in the sacrificial fire of arms. Does the beloved 'kulajā Lakṣmī' also double for a lady of a respectable family whom Vajradeva married with the rise of his power? Otherwise marriage with Vijaya-Śrī alluded to in the same verse later would appear unduly repetitive.

Verse 32 mentions some of Vajradeva's sterling qualities. Passionate and swift in truth (rāgo dravo ca satye), he is skilful as an orator in public and not in spreading calumny about others (n=āpavāde parasya). His proficiency in scriptures does not keep away from darkness (=the ignorant ones). Even if he is deceived, he continues to address the needs of the subjects (vañcane (') pi praj=ārthāḥ). There is no let up in his charity (kṣāntir=dāne na). He fights his enemy face to face (and only) when the latter is armed (i.e. he maintains the ethical code of a hero in not striking an unsuspecting unarmed enemy from behind). With him, friendship and sacrifice had priority to attraction of the fair sex. Scholars have failed to read many of the words employed in this stanza correctly and their translations have also suffered as a result (see Check lists).

V. 33 speaks of his fame (its soothing quality) derived from the abode of the moon (indu-dhāma-kalito and not Indra-dhāma-kalito as read by scholars) spreading over the lotus-like faces of the wives of the stubborn enemies. It is as (pleasant) to them as consecration in the holy water of the Gaṅgā is to the nobles (āryeṣu) and as anointment with thick sandal-wood paste is to the maidens of the quarters.

Hoping for long duration of this Kīrtti: Verse 34

In V. 34 the poet wishes that the meritorious act of the achiever would attain fame (vrajatu....pratiṣṭhām) for as long as long as the skies of the goose, expert by nature (in directing the goose to its course), endure; the light of

truth, the dispeller of darkness (i.e. the sun) illuminates all the directions; and the Tortoise performs the extraordinary feat of bearing the volume of the earth. Scholars have erroneously read 'bhavyasy=aitāḥ' and have made a mess of the expression 'tāvat=tasya vrajatu kṛtinah kīrtir=eṣā pratiṣṭhām.' R&I have correctly read 'vrajatu' (√vraj=to go, to proceed, to attain, etc. + lot-tu) in the text, but have inadvertently treated it as a personal name Vajraṭa which again they have confounded with Vajradeva, c.f. 'eulogy (of Vrajata)', op. cit., p. 29. SCM has read 'Vrajata' in the text itself and has treated it as a personal name in the translation, cf. 'work of Vrajata' (P.S., p. 70). Furthermore, he has made the gratuitous remark : 'There is a word, reading 'Vrajata' in this verse, which the learned editors of the charter in the Ep. India (sic) have read as 'Vrajata'. They have suggested that it was the name of the composer'. (ibid., p. 60). Following an earlier reading of SCM, ACS has stated that the name of the composer of the inscription is 'Vrajabhṛiti'. As a matter of fact, this inscription does not mention the name of its composer. KKG also has failed to read some words and read some words wrongly, e.g. 'dhvajata' for 'vrajatu'. Similar verses hoping for long duration of a meritorious deed is quite common in epigraphs.

Engraver: Sāmanta Śrī-Māhaṭa: line 73 (prose)

Verse 34 is followed by the last line (line 73 of the inscription which is much shorter than the other lines and is carefully centred. It is in prose and states that this (copper plate) charter has been engraved (utkīrṇam=idam śāsanam) by the feudatory chief,⁵² the illustrious Māhaṭa (Sāmanta Śrī-Māhaṭena). The similarity of the name Māhaṭa with the name Māhaṭā, the queen of Devapāla (and mother of Mahendrapāla) is interesting. Besides, he was a man of some importance as is indicated by his designation 'sāmanta'⁵². It has been suggested by one scholar that probably he was a brother of Māhaṭā (SCM, Pratna-samīkṣā, vol. 6-8, p. 59). Nothing definite can be said on this in the absence of more positive evidence.

Check List of Errors / Differences in the Published Readings : List No. 1

Serial No.	Verse/Line	(I) S. C. Mukherji: SCM-1	(II) A. Chattopadhyay Shastri: ACS	(III) Our version: SCB
1.	1; 2-3	subhūtinanditam sadā na priyaḥ	nityam vandiganaiśca vanditamanādānapriyaḥ	su(sva) bhūti-nandi- tamanā dāna-priyaḥ
2.	2; 4-5	svasya doṣānta- kāri	sva(su)doṣāntakāri	dhvasta doṣ= āndhakāro
3.	3; 5	guṇayutam..... ñjanā	guṇavantam..... jātā	guṇaratnam..... jātā (am)
4.	4; 7	yasyandenaiva		yasy=endun=eva
5.	4; 7	samavetān Indra- rājādikān	samare tā Indra- rājādikāḥ	samare tān=Indra- rāj=ādikān
6.	4; 7-8	Sindhūnāmādhip- stamadhvarajasāda	Sindhūnāmādhipam pramathya rabhasād	Sindhūnām= adhipam= pramathya rabhasā
7.	4; 8	vikrāntibhāje nija	vikrāntibhājā nijā	vikrāntibhājō(ā) nijā
8.	4; 8-9	Cakrāyudhārthine	Cakrāyudhāyārthine	Cakrāyudh=ārthine
9.	5; 9	vātāddharavisiñci- nyetāni māsyat	vātā haranti siñcya- ntyetan hi mādyat	vātā haranti siñcany- (nty)=etāni mādyat
10.	5; 10	vārddha sevopa (pā) sanām	rājñām senāparāṇām	rājñām sevāparāṇām=
11.	6; 10-11	Nītervilāsa- bhuvanapriya	Nītervilāsa- bhuvanapriya	Nīter=vvilāsa- bhavanam=priya
12.	6; 11	jagatyudadhīn	jagatyudadhīn	jagat=padavīn
13.	7; 11-12	duṣṭevanīrikānekai	dūropanītakanakai	daṇḍ=opanīta- kanaka
14.	7; 12	rājña		rājā

(I) SCM-1 : From Saṁskṛita Sāhitya Parishat Patrikā, vol. LXVII

(II) ACS : From Pāl Abhilekh Saṅgraha

(III) : Same as our version

Serial No.	Verse/Line	(I) S. C. Mukherji: SCM-1	(II) A. Chattopadhyay Shastri: ACS	(III) Our version: SCB
15.	7; 12	nirmime	nirmame	nirmite(ta)
16.	7; 12	grihañca śauryāya kautukañca tilakañca	grihañca ramyañ śauryāya kautuka- karañca	grihañca Gauryā yat =kautukañca tilakañca
17.	8; 13		labdhodyamaḥ	labdh=odayaṃ
18.	8; 13-14	puñjita vahnīṣu	sangrāme hatavairi	khadg=āvarjītai (ta)-vairi
19.	8; 14	niḥśeṣabhūbhrīd- bhṛīṣāṃ		niḥśeṣa-bhu(ū)- bhṛīd=bhuvām(m)
20.	9; 14	yodhayāmāsura- ra (asura) ya		yodhayāmāsura= arāyaya=te
21.	9; 15	vivasvadramaṇā- va-īni (?)	vivasvadramaṇā vadhīni	vivasvad= bhramaṇ=āvadhīni
22.	10; 16	durgādhāśca Himālayācala- dravaḥ	durvādhaśca Himā- layācalavaraḥ	durgāyāś=ca Himālay=ācala- bhavaḥ
23.	10; 16	ślāghyaḥ kara- sthaḥ dhṛitaḥ	ślāghyaḥ karasthaḥ kṛitaḥ	ślāghyaḥ=karaḥ= grihnatā
24.	11; 17-18	straiyīmivoha	striyaṃ kilovāha	s=Traiṭim=iv=oha (odha)
25.	12; 18		saukarmato	saukaryato
26.	13; 19	yasyāśvā vijaya- pathāni	yasyāśvīyagate patheṣu	yasy=āśvā-vijaya- prayāṇe
27.	13; 20	vidyāmṛitānāika- hetumanjapa (sa?) mvidyādharaṅg- aṅḥ	vidyabhyasadiyā tathā ca mananaṃ vidhyādharaṅg- abhūt	vidyām=utpatan= aika-hetum=ajapan =Vidyādharaṅg- (m)=gaṅḥ
28.	14; 21	vṛiṣabhakuṇḍāgra (pa)ratvasthalād	vṛiṣakuṇḍākhyā ratnasthalād	vṛiṣabha-kṣuṇḍ= āgra-ratna-sthalād
29.	14; 21	nyālohitāntarjja-lāt	nyālohitāntarjja-lāt	vyāloḍit=āntarjja-lāt

Serial No.	Verse/Line	(I) S. C. Mukherji: SCM-1	(II) A. Chattopadhyay Shastri: ACS	(III) Our version: SCB
30.	14; 21-22	-āparādrūmukhekā- dhityakāñca śai- ladrapādbhūbhujē	-āparādīnmukhācca niyataṃ mānauja- sāṃ bhūbhujām	-āpara-dīn=mukh= aika-tillakāt śaila- dvayād=bhūbhujō(ā)
31.	14; 22	bhrūrānate mau- libhiḥ	bhrūrānate mau- libhiḥ	dūr=ānatair= mmaulibhiḥ
32.	15; 22-23	khadgāghāta mahe- bhangam (=Mah dayam?)bhuvīṭṭalat	khadgāghāta Mahendrakumbha- vigalat	khadg=otkhāta- mah=ebha- kumbha-vigalat
33.	15; 23	santīryādhipatīn dhām pratidīśaṃ	santīryāpi patīn sadā pratidīśaṃ	santīry=āpi patīn= apām=pratidīśaṃ
33a.	15; 24	ścitramvādhaka kāraṇe	ścitram vādhaka kāraṇair-	ś=citram=vādhaka- kāraṇai(nvai)r-
34.	16; 24	jayaśriyāñcā	jayaśriyāñca	jayaśriy=ārthī
35.	16; 24-25	praṇayīṇī bhava- to'mā (-- sam?)	praṇayi me bhavato mano hi	praṇayīṇī bhavato= 'ham=āsam
36.	16; 25	itthampriyā	itthampriyā	itthambhiyā
37.	31-32	Kubjayatikāyā	Kubjayatikā	Kubjaghatikā
38.	32	Kāsikkata-vandhāka	Kāsmigadavandhāka	Kāsiggāda-bandhāka
39.	32-33	Ś(S) rotayinirjha- reṇa Jambha (ñkri?)- vāsakā	srotasi nirjhareṇa Jambūvāsaka- khātena	Golayi-nirjhareṇ =Ājagara-vāsak= āvakhātena
40.	33-34	Nandāsurolyāttu	Nandasurālyāt tu	Nandasur=ālyā(h)
41.	37	gomahīṣyājāvikā-	gomahīṣājāvikā	go-mahīṣy=ajāvikā
42.	39	Varijadevena	Śrī Vajradevena	Śrī-Vajradevena
43.	40	vasundharāśce	vasundharāyāśca	ca satvarāśeḥ
44.	40-41	mahāvihāraḥ kāritaḥ	mahāvihāraḥ kāritaḥ	mayā vihāraḥ kāritaḥ
45.	42	dharmanetrī- sthānasya	dharmanetrī- sthānasya	dharmanetrī- sthānasya

Serial No.	Verse/Line	(I) S. C. Mukherji: SCM-1	(II) A. Chattopadhyay Shastri: ACS	(III) Our version: SCB
46.	42	ārya Vaivarttika	ārya Vaivarttika	āry=Āvaivarttika
47.	42-43	yathārdhe pudgadga (dga) laśca tadādyar ddham cīvara pariṣ-kārādyarddham	pūjanāśana cīvara pariṣka (ā) rādyar- tham	yath=ārham pūjana- lekhan=ādy=artham cīvara...pariṣkār= ādy=artham
48.	44	Bhaṭṭārapādā dadatviti	Bhaṭṭārapādāva- dadāt	Bhaṭṭārapādā dadatv=iti
49.	44-45	ato'smābhista (corrected sma)- dīya vijñaptaye	ato'smābhirasmadiya vijñaptiyā	ato='smābhis= tadiya vijñaptiyā
49a.	46-47	yathārdhamapi... mayābhimatānām- āpra(tpa)rikalpita	anyeśāmapi.... mamābhimatānām parikalpita	anyeśām=api...mam =ābhimatānām= parikalpita
50.	47	tathaiva prabhavaḥ		tath=aiva pra- dattaḥ
51.	47	yato	matvā	ato
52.	49	bhāvibhirapiṇḍa- pātabhi		bhāvibhir=api bhūpatibhir-
53.	49	gauravopaharaṇe	gauravāpaharaṇe	gauravād=apa- haraṇe
54.	21; 53-54	Śrīmāssāt-sāma- tāreṇā kṛitaḥ (overwritten by hand)	Śrīman mahāmatā rekhākṛitā sva- kṛita	Śrīmat-Saṅgrāma- tāreṇa kṛitaḥ sukṛita
55.	22.; 54	Śrīmān (Māhata?) kule mahati		Śrīmān kule mahati
56.	22; 54	ndeva ca Daha- varmma (over- written by hand)		Devaradeva-nāmā
57.	23; 55-56	anyonya śraddhayā	ananyaśraddhayā	anyo(=')nya-spardd- hayā

Serial No.	Verse/Line	(I) S. C. Mukherji: SCM-1	(II) A. Chattopadhyay Shastri: ACS	(III) Our version: SCB
58.	25; 59	kīrtisthalānām	kīrtistanoti	kīrttis=tatāna
59.	27; 62	-rmaṇḍale Darda (rbha) raṇyāṇī	-rmaṇḍale Dar- durānte	-rmaṇḍale Darddaraṇ- ḍyam
60.	28; 63	ca prabhūto kirti- lokamva (ha)ntī	vapustrilokī- tilakam vahantī	vapus=tri(stri) lo- kī-tilakam=vahantī
61.	29; 64	Lakṣmīrutānapada- vatāsvapratīṣṭhā- daya-	Lakṣmīrutānapadeva yā svapati-hṛidaya-	Lakṣmīr=ut=ālaya devatā svapati- hṛidaya-
62.	29; 64	Sunīmarundhatībhi	Sunīti vārundhatī	satī kim=Arundhatī
63.	29; 64	Vasudhāreyamvitta- prasādhita	Vasudhāre yaścitta- prasādhita	Vasudhār=eyam= vitta-prasādhita-
64.	30; 65	devī dattasyāravi- denavṛittadhāmeva	divīva tasyām draviṇ- āvṛitena dhāmeṣa	div=īva tasyām raviṇ=eva tena dhām=eva
65.	30; 65	samyagvidhinā kriyādi		samyag=vidhin= odapādi
66.	30; 65-66	satvodhanakilasva- taḥ pratāpī	satvopakāram kurute pratāpī	satv=opakār=aika- -rataḥ pratāpī
67.	31; 66	khadgāghāto	khadgarañjita	khadg=āvarjjita
68.	32; 68	(difficult to make out for overwritten correction)	loke'smin..... pūjanārtham	Rāgo dravo..... ca praj=ārthāḥ
69.	32; 69	tiṣṭhopyadhvare		dviṣati raṇavare
70.	32; 69	tyāge sthīre bhū- bhṛit-lavanitā	tyāge sthīro bhud- bhujacalavanitā	tyāge sthīre(o') bhun=na tu cala vanitā
71.	33; 69-70	ārya Prajñāpāramitā Śrīpu(?) līlābhīṣeko	ārya prabhā pari- sar salīlābhīṣeko	āryeṣu Jahnu-tanayā ś(s)alīl=ābhīṣeko
72.	33; 70	saundaryam	Mahendradhāma-gatinā	yasy=endu-dhāma-

Serial No.	Verse/Line	(I) S. C. Mukherji: SCM-1	(II) A. Chattopadhyay Shastri: ACS	(III) Our version: SCB
		kavitāyā murtyate	yaśasā pradattaḥ	kalito yaśasām vitānaḥ
73.	34; 71	imeḥ ślokāḥ prakṛiti-paṭuvo dhādvande Buddhastavaḥ	bhuñjan kāmān prakṛiti-paṭudhī bhūpatirgām cirāya	Han(m)sasy=aitāḥ prakṛiti-paṭavo yāvad=ev=eha gāvah
74.	34; 71	dattvālokaṁ tatva- vedānudīpikaṁ	tattvālokaṁ vihata- tamaśaṁ varttate sarvadikṣu	tatv=ālokaṁ vihata- tamaśaḥ tanvate sarvva-dikkaṁ
75.	34; 71-72	prithvītalapra- vato su(sū?)ryaruṣ -mā ca kūrmmah	prithvīvalaya- vahula śreyasaḥ samsthitiḥ syāt	prithvī-valaya- vahan=āścarya- karmma(ā) ca ku(ū) rmmah
76.	34; 72	tāvattasya Vraja- bhṛitinaḥ kīrtti- reṣā pratiṣṭhām	tāvad Vajrākhyā- manujapateḥ kīrtti- reṣā pratiṣṭhet	tāvat=tasya vrajatu kṛitinaḥ kīrtti=eṣā pratiṣṭhām

Check List of Errors / Differences in the Published Readings : List No. 2

Sl. No.	Verse/Line	(I) Kamala Kanta Gupta KKG	(II) S.C. Mukherji SCM-2	(III) K.V.Ramesh & S. Iyer R&I	(IV) Our Version SCB
1.	1. 2.		A(t)yānanda	A[t*]y=ananda	ary=ānanda
2.	.. 2-3	sabhūtivandita manādāna-	subhuti-nandita- mahā-dāna-	subhūti-handi- ta mahā-dāna-	su(sva)bhūti- nanditamaṇā dāna-
3.	.. 4.	prajāhitakarā			prajā-hitakaro
4.	2. 4-5	sva sva doṣān- dhakāro			dhvasta-doṣ= āndhakāro
5.	.. 5.	paṭa	paṭa	paṭa	paṭu
6.		guṇavantaṁ	guṇavantam		guṇa-ratnaṁ
7.	3. 6.		dviṣad=aneka	dvishad=aneka	dviṣad=anīka
8.	.. 7.		yasy=Endradeva	yasy=Endradeva	yasy=(e)ndun =eva
9.	4. 8.			-pramadhya	-pramathya
10.			nirvyāja(m) ānati	nirvyāja[m*] nati	nirvyāj=ānati
11.	.. 8-9	Cakrāyudhā (dhaprā) rthine	Cakrāyudhāy= ārthine	Cakrāyudhaya[r] thine	Cakrāyudh= ārthine
12.	5. 9.		siñcaty=etāni	sincaty=etāni	siñcany(nty)= etāni
13.			jalad=dāna		galad=dāna
14.	6. 10-11	bhuvanam	bhuvanam		bhavanam

- (I) KKG : From Itihās (33rd year), and Pūrvādri (year 12)
 (II) SCM-2 : From Pratna Samiksha, vol. 6-8
 (III) R&I : From Epigraphia Indica, vol. XLII
 (IV) : Same as our version

Sl. No.	Verse/Line	(I) Kamala Kanta Gupta KKG	(II) S.C. Mukherji SCM-2	(III) K.V.Ramesh & S. Iyer R&I	(IV) Our Version SCB
15.	11.	jagatyudadhīn			jagat=padavīn
16.	..	śa(sam)kramyate			śam(ś=cam) kramyate
17.	7.	11-12 da(dū)ropanīta			daṇḍ=opanīta
18.	..	nirmmime	nirmmime	nirmmime	nirmmite(ta)
19.	..		śaurya		Gauryā
20.	8.	13-14 khādyavarjita			khadg= āvarjita
21.	..	14.	vāraṇa ghaṭā	vāraṇa ghaṭā	vāraṇa -saṭā
22.	..	15.	kṣetramiṣṭānya-		kretum=iṣṭāny =a-
23.	9.	15-16 nīcitambibhratā			nī=ci(m ci) ram=bibhratā
24.	10.	16.	huta	huta	hṛita
25.	..	..	ślāghyani=ka-		ślāghyan=ka-
26.	..	..	samyakatvam	samyaktvam	samyak-svam
27.	11.	17-18 (strai) () (yī)- mivāha sulakṣa- aṅgīm	straiyīm-iv- odvāha sulakṣa- ṅgīm	traī (s=tra)- yīm-iv-o[dvā*]ha salakṣhaṅ-āṅgīm	s=Traiīm=iv= oha(oḍha) sa(su)lakṣa- ṅgīm
28.	13.	19.		yasy=aśvā vijaya- pathān....vyūha	yasy=aśā vijaya-pra- yāṇe....vyūhe pu(ū)rit=āmba- (ra)tayā
30.	..	20.		drume	bhrame
31.	..	..		añjayan	ajayan
32.	14.	21.		kuṇḍākhyā	kṣuṇṇ=āgra

Sl. No.	Verse/Line	(I) Kamala Kanta Gupta KKG	(II) S.C. Mukherji SCM-2	(III) K.V.Ramesh & S. Iyer R&I	(IV) Our Version SCB
33.	..		viśikhany=āloḍit-		viśikha- vyāloḍit-
34.	..	22.		mukhaik= ādhityakāt	mukh=aika- tilakāt
35.	..	..		dūrānantair-	dūr=ānantair-
36.	15.	23.	santīryāpi patīna-dhām-	santīry=ādhipatīn -apām	santīry=āpi patīn=apām
37.	..	24.	(sū) trambādha- ka-kāranair-		ś=citram= [pava] ka- haraṇair-
38.	16.	..	tvaṁ (taṁ)		Tvaṁ
39.	..	24-25	bhavatīhamā(na)- sam(m)		bhavato='ham āsam
40.	..	25.	vyājaghniire/ vyājaṣmire	vyājṛimbhire	vyājṛimbhire
		Line			
40.	25-26			nan-adhipa dhara	nānāvidha khara
41.	28.			dhūli-prasarita	dhūli-dhūsa- rita
42.	..	pādātābhara	pādātābhara	padān=a-bhara	pādātā(ta)- bhara
43.	31.			Auddālakhātaka	Kuddālakhā- taka
44.	29.	pādāntam dhyātāḥ			pād=ānu- dhyātāḥ
45.	31.			Kunda[1a] khātaka	Ku(ddāla)- khātaka
46.	31.		paricchinna	Paricchhinna	paricchinnā

Sl. No.	Verse/Line	(I) Kamala Kanta Gupta KKG	(II) S.C. Mukherji SCM-2	(III) K.V.Ramesh & S. Iyer R&I	(IV) Our Version SCB
47.	31-32		Yotikā		ghatikā
48.	32.		Kāsiggara- bandhāka	Kāsiggara- Vammaka	Kāsiggaḍa- bandhāka
49.	„		Golaṭi	Golaṭi	Golayī
50.	33.	(ni) (dhā) ja(sā) Vāsakāvakhātena	na Jambu-vāsak- āvakhātena	n-Aja[ga]ra- vasak-avakhātena	n=Ājagara- vāsak= āvakhātena
51.	„		Svalpa-Nandā- pāra	portion left out	Svalpa-Nandā- (dhā or pā)ra
52.	„	nirjjata	Vijjaga- bandhakam	Vijjaga vandhakam	Bijjaga- bandhākam
53.	34.	saṅgalāntar-	saṅgal-antar-	Shaṅgal-antar-	saṅ=ṅal=āntar-
54.	„			Nandasurālpā	Nandasur= ālyā
55.	36-37	dausādhassā- dhyanika	dau(h)sādha- sādhanika		dau(h)sādhyā- sādhanika
56.	38.	no'nyāṅgam	no=nyaṅca (nyamś=ca)	no='nyaṅch (nyamś=ch)=a	no='nyāṅsa (m=śca)
57.	40.	vasundharāśreḥ	ca satvaraścaḥ		ca satvarāśeḥ
58.	40-41. mayā viharah		mahāvihārah		
59.	41.		Nandadīrghik- odraṅge	Nandadīrghik- odraṅga(ṅgo)	Nandadīrghik =odrangam
60.	42-43.	pūjānala-khādyā- nnādyartham	pūjana-lekha (pa)n-ādy-arthe	pūjana lekha (pa)n-ādy-arthe	pūjana-lekhan =ādy=artham
61.	43.		samādhān-ady- artham		samādhān= ārtham
62.	44.	Śrīmadbhāṭāraka-			Śrīmad=Bhaṭ-

Sl. No.	Verse/Line	(I) Kamala Kanta Gupta KKG	(II) S.C. Mukherji SCM-2	(III) K.V.Ramesh & S. Iyer R&I	(IV) Our Version SCB
					pādā dadatvi- (ti) ti
					tātraka-pādā dadatv=iti (i.e. dadatu iti)
63.	44-45.	ato'smābhira- smadīyarvijñā- ptyā			Ato='smābhis =tādīya vijñā- ptyā
64.	46.			sa-paṭṭa	saghaṭṭa
65.	„			sa-daś-apachā (rā)rah(dhah)	sadaś= āpacārah
66.	49		narakapāt	naraka-pātaka	naraka-pāta-
67.	21. 53-54	Śrīmatsa jñāmatā rekhākṛiteḥ	Śrīmān Saṅgr- āmatāreṇa kṛitam		Śrīmat-Saṅgr- āmatāreṇa kṛitaḥ
68.	22. 55.		sad-guṇa-kath- āśrya eka eva		sad=guṇa- kathāsu ya eka eva
69.	23. 55-56	anyonyāspadva- yo-vṛiddhamanya mananya			Anyo(=')nya -sparddhayā vṛiddham= ananya-
70.	25 57-58	sphara (sphurat)			sphāra-dhārā
71.	„ 59.	kīrtistathā- nandaṁ			kīrttis=tatāna
72.	26. 59.		pūritārtha-	pūrit-ārtha-	pūrit=ārthi-
73.	„ 59-60	dhiṣaṇaḥ (no) vijñāta vastrasthiti(h)			dhiṣaṇā vijñā- ta-vastu-sthiti- (h)
74.	„ 60.	rūpane(nne) tra	kurvan=netra	kurvane(n=ne)tra	rūpaṁ netra
74a.	„ 60.	vayasyābhavat			-va yasy= ābhavat

Sl. No.	Verse/Line	(I) Kamala Kanta Gupta KKG	(II) S.C. Mukherji SCM-2	(III) K.V.Ramesh & S. Iyer R&I	(IV) Our Version SCB
75.	27. 61.	Vahnirvvairin- dha-nāmbharṇṇ- paśata-	Vahnir=vvair= in-dhanānām=ṇṇipa- śata-		Vahnir=vvair= īndhanānām nn(mn)aya- śata-
76.		sarōjākarārkāya- māliḥ			sarōj=ākar= ārkāyamāṇ(n)- aḥ
77.	.. 62.			Darddaranyām (nyām)	Darddarandy- ām(m)
78.	28. 63.	vadhūstri (stri)- lokī			vapus=tri (ri)- lokī
79.	29. 64.	lolām (lā)	līnā	līnā	līlā
80.			lakṣmīr= Uttānapādeva		Lakṣmīr=ut= ālāya-devatā
81.			Sunīti v=Ārun- dhatī		satī kim= Arundhatī
82.		vasudhāreyam= vitta prasādhi- tamandirāt	vasudhār=eyam= vitta-prasādhi- mandira	vasudhār= eyam=vitta- prasādhi- mandira	vasudhār= eyam=vitta- prasādhi- mandirā
83.	.. 65.	lokāmśca kārya			lokāmś= cakāra
84.	30. ..	dhāmeva samy- ag-vidhino(da)- pādi	Rāmena samyag- viditogg(g)- uṇādi	Rāmeva samyag= vidino(to) ggu (gu)ṇ=ādi	dhām=eva samyag= vidhin= odapādi
85.	.. 65-66	sattopakāram karataḥ			satv=opakār= aika-rataḥ
86.	32. 68.	tyāgo dravye ca satye	tyāgo durvo(bo)- dha-satye	Tyāgo durvvo (bo)dha-satye	Rāgo dravo ca satye

Sl. No.	Verse/Line	(I) Kamala Kanta Gupta KKG	(II) S.C. Mukherji SCM-2	(III) K.V.Ramesh & S. Iyer R&I	(IV) Our Version SCB
87.			parastāt	parastāt	parasya
88.			nanartta	nanartta	na jātu
89.		prajāyāḥ	praj=ārkaḥ	praj=ārkaḥ	praj=ārthāḥ
90.		kṣāntirdīne (...) yo	kṣāntir=dīnena bhūyo	kṣāntir=dīne na bhūyo	kṣāntir=dāne na bhūyo
91.	32. 69.	(bhrū(ha)nu) cala-vanitāmsa (tām sa) marayogepi			sthire(o=') bhun=na tu cala-vanitā- samprayoge (=')pi
92.	33. 69-70	arci(rciḥ) ṣu juhvata tayā	Ārya-Prajñāpāra- mitā śrīṣu		āryeṣu Jahnu- tanayā-śa(sa)-
93.	33. 70.	kalito ma () () () ()	yasy=Endra- dhāma-kalito yaśasām vitānaḥ	yasy=Endra- dhāma-kalito yaśasām vitānaḥ	yasy=endu- dhāma-kalito- yaśasām vitānaḥ
94.	34. 71.	() () (bhī) tāḥ	Bhavyasy= aitāḥ	Bhavyasy= aitāḥ	Han(m)sasy= aitāḥ
95.		prakṛitipata (dho) plāvadeve (ndra) gāvaḥ			prakṛiti-paṭavo yāvad=ev= eha gāvaḥ
96.		tattvālokaṁ nihata tamasah tattvate			tatv=ālokaṁ vihata-tamasah tanvate
97.		sarvadicṣu	sarvva-dikṣam		sarvva-dikkaṁ
98.	.. 72	dhvajata kṛitinaḥ	Vrajata kṛiti- naḥ		vrajatu kṛitinaḥ
99.		pratiṣṭhām (pratiṣṭhā)			pratiṣṭhām(m)
100.	- 73.			Māhadena	Māhaṭena

NOTES

Introductory Observations

1. Unfortunately, this important journal has failed to come out for quite some time which has caused concern and dismay in the concerned academic circle. It is expected that the authorities would take urgent steps to resume publication of this journal without delay.
2. The following are just some examples (serial numbering and diacritical marks are mine) :-
 - (i) In the Jagjibanpur c.p. there is a eulogisation of Mahendrapāla's forefathers beginning from Vapyata, father of Gopāla (p. 174);
 - (ii) That Dharmmapāla became the lord of the seven seas or the seven rivers of the Indus system has also been recorded in this grant (ibid.);
 - (iii) The wife of king Dharmmapāla was Raṅṅādevī, which has been written as Reṅyadevī in this inscription. She has been described in this inscription as the 'strīdharma incarnate' (p. 176);
 - (iv) King Mahendrapāla is said to have conquered a vast territory extending from ... the Indus river to the Lauhitya or Brahmaputra... He probably also killed the enemies in the land of Kanauj with his sword (p. 175);
 - (v) During his victorious campaigns... the king (Mahendrapāla) made it a point to propagate the ideals of Buddhism there and the 'Hetuvidyā' (p. 174);
 - (vi) The name of the preceptor of the king was probably Śrī Manasanarayana or Śrī Matsanaranjana (p. 176);
 - (vii) There is probably a reference to the erection of three temples of square type by the king by the side of the Nanda Lake (ibid.);
 - (viii) It is not clear whether Mahāsenāpati Barggadeva was killed in a fierce battle and his wife Lajjādevī went to the Mahāvihāra erected by her husband with his brother-in-law as indicated in lines 67-68 of this inscription (ibid.);
 - (ix) The inscription seems to have been composed by one Vrajabhṛti or Vrajabhuti (p. 173).

Text

1. The reading 'mān=māni' is rather hypothetical.
2. R&I read aty=ānanda.
3. The letter preceding dāna looks like nā or rā, but not hā.
4. Read paṭa by other scholars.
5. Read aneka by other scholars.
6. R&I read yasy=Endradeva.
7. R&I read pramadhya(thya).
8. vikrānti-bhāje nija[m*] nirvyāja[m*] nati—read by R&I.
9. R&I read Cakrāyudhāy=ārthine, which may be metrically justified.

10. R&I read siṅcaty=ctāni.
11. R&I read nirmame
12. The original has sardma.
13. SCM reads Śauryā.
14. SCM sees a duplication of kan here. Actually his own reading of kautukaṅ (for tila-) at the end of the preceding line is wrong.
15. Other scholars read ghaṭā.
16. R&I read huta.
17. R&I read bhṛṣam(śam).
18. R&I read samyaktvam.
19. R&I read trayīm-iv-o[dvā*]jha.
20. R&I read prayāṇa-.
21. R&I read drume.
22. R&I read ajapan.
23. SCM reads Kuṇḍākhyā.
24. SCM reads adhityakāt.
25. R&I read dūr-ānantarair-.
26. R&I read adhipatim.
27. R&I read [pāya]ka-haraṇair-.
28. R&I read vyājṛimbhire.
29. R&I read nānādhipa.
30. R&I read dhara.
31. R&I read prasarita.
32. R&I read pādān-ā-bhara.
33. R&I read Auddālakhātaka.
34. R&I read Kunda[la]khātaka.
35. Read srotah. Palatal sibilant also occurs in śrotikayā (line 32) and śroto(=')vadhiḥ (line 35).
36. R&I read Kāsiggara-Vammaka in the Text and Kāsīnjara and Vammaka in the Translation.
37. R&I read Golaṭi and Ajaravāsaka in the Text, while in the Translation the latter is reduced to Jāgaravāsaka (p. 17, also p. 26).
38. The portion 'Svalpa-Nandādhāra (or pāra) paścima-paṭena vilva-vṛikṣeṇa' fails to occur in R&I's Text, but is included in the Translation.
39. The letter preceding 'ra' can be read either as dhā or pā. We prefer the former.
40. R&I read Ṣaṇḍal-āntar-.
41. The original has pūrvvāmukhoścattarakuṇḍā The intended reading may be pūrvvāmukhās=c-ottara-kuṇḍā(h) meaning 'and the east-facing kuṇḍas on the north'. R&I suggest that the engraver had originally written the letter u after kho and subsequently cancelled it. In our view, the letter following kho is śca.

42. R&I read Nandasurālpā.
43. The punctuation mark here serves the purpose of a comma.
44. R&I read= 'nyāñch(nyāñś=ch)=achāta'.
45. SCM, KKG, ACS read mahā (vihārah).
46. R&I read -odraṅga(ṅgo) and comment 'There is an unnecessary punctuation mark here'. SCM also shows a punctuation mark here. They fail to recognise this fore-runner of the Bengali type of anusvāra and mistake it for a punctuation mark.
47. R&I read lekh(pa)n-ādy-arthe.
48. R&I read samādhān-ādy-artham.
49. KKG, SCM-I and ACS read ato'smābhir=asmadīya.
50. R&I read sa-paṭṭa.
51. R&I emend it as sa-daś=āparādhāh which is uncalled for as both the forms occur in inscriptions.
52. R&I take no notice of this punctuation mark here.
53. Punctuation mark here serves as a comma.
54. R&I read naraka-pātaka.
55. R&I read kath-āśraya.
56. The double daṇḍa noticed here by R&I appears to be superfluous marks.
57. R&I read amalinatara-vāri-.
58. R&I read pūrit=ārtha-.
59. R&I read satyan=nirmmita.
60. R&I read kurvane(n=ne)tra-.
61. R&I read nṛipa-.
62. R&I read Darddaraṅyām(nyām). GB also reads Darddaraṅī as the name of the maṇḍala.
63. The punctuation mark is unnecessary.
64. R&I read Rām=eva.
65. R&I read vidino(to)ggu(gu)ṅ=ādi.
66. R&I read daya(dha)t.
67. Punctuation mark is unnecessary here.
68. R&I read durvvo(bo)dha.
69. R&I read parastāt.
70. R&I read nanartta (for na jātu).
71. R&I read praj=ārkkah.
72. R&I read kṣāntir=dīne.
73. R&I notice a redundant stroke (punctuation mark) here, but it is not visible in the plate.
74. R&I and others read yasy=Endra-dhāma-.
75. R&I read Bhavyasy=aitāh.

76. Equivalent to diśam (from diś). Cf. Williams, M. Monier, Sanskrit-English Dictionary, for dikka.
77. R&I read Māhaḍena.

Translation

1. Though it is also possible to read the letter preceding bhūti as su, we prefer to read it as sva, as it gives a better meaning.
2. For clarification about the reading, see Discussion and Analysis.
3. R&I's translation, 'His fame, like that of Indra', stems from their reading yas=Endradeva-yaśasā.
4. Some of the words of this verse have not been read correctly by R&I and this has affected their translation also.
5. R&I translate the expression hata-ripu-mahiṣī as 'the dying queens of the enemy kings'.
6. R&I have wrongly interpreted the expression, taking Vikramā as the name a second queen of Dharmapāla. For further details, see Discussion and Analysis.
7. The use of the singular number for the pronoun (yat) and the adjectives - kautukañ=ca and tilakañ=ca seem to suggest that Sugata and Gaurī were enshrined in a common temple. Alternately, the pronoun and the adjectives are applied only to the abode (temple) of Gaurī, which immediately precedes these.
8. This aspect of the expression 'dharmasya prasavena' has escaped the attention of scholars.
9. R&I fail to realise that Kāmarūpa with respect to Devapāla has reference to Assam.
10. For details regarding Devapāla's exploits in Assam and the Himalayan region see Discussion and Analysis.
11. As has been rightly pointed out by R&I, it draws sustenance (in the eyes of the composer) from the epithet paramēśvara assumed by the Pāla kings.
12. R&I read the word as trayī (in trayīm=iva, translated as: like the three Vedas).
13. R&I wrongly read drume for bhrame and translate the expression sampādit =orvvī-drume (as read by them) as: 'created an impression of making the earth appear like a tree (p. 25, and also p. 20, note 2).
14. Read as 'vyājṛimbhire' by R&I and translated as increased (the pleasure), lending a diametrically opposite view to Mahendrapāla's attitude to war.
15. The name of the jayaskandhāvāra is read as Auddālakhātaka by R&I.
16. Svalpanandā sounds like an antonym of Mahānandā and may have been a smaller river in the area.
17. R&I's reading Ṣaṇḍal-āntar-is wrong. They take Ṣaṇḍala as the name of a place.
18. Derived from duṣṣādhyā-sādhana.
19. Or, residents and (ca) cultivators.
20. R&I's translation: 'I gave as if directly by myself (bhaṭṭāarakapādā)' is wrong.
21. Wrongly read as Nandadīrghik-odraṅga(ṅgo) by R&I.

22. Lekhana is unnecessarily emended to lepana and translated as ointment by R&I.
23. About the wrong attribution of Vajradeva's work to Mahendrapāla by R&I and others, and for correct interpretation of the passage, see Discussion and Analysis.
24. Not properly translated by R&I.
25. Read by R&I as sa-paṭṭa-tar-opetaḥ and translated as 'with yajña trees' (p. 27)
26. The four verses, Nos. 17 to 20, are common in Pāla inscriptions.
27. Is this used as sort of a biruda (GB), or just an epithet of Mahendrapāla?
28. Translated by R&I as : 'which could not be comprehended by anybody'.
29. It is difficult to accept 'stature' as the proper translation (cf. R&I) of guruṇā; it would have done for a word like gauravena or gurutvena.
30. R&I read the expression as amalinatara-vāri which they translate as 'like crystal clear white pure water.'
31. The translation of R&I do not give expression to the different words of this verse, some of which they read differently.
32. Read as Darddaraṇyāṁ(nyām) by R&I according to whom the name of the maṇḍala is Darddaraṇya (pp. 9, 18). KKG and ACS are of the view that it was Nārāyaṇadeva who made Dharmapāla the ruler of the maṇḍala of Darddaraṇḍī. For details, see Discussion and Analysis.
33. Alternately, Satī can be taken as a proper name to mean Satī, the consort of Śiva, who is held as the model of chastity.
34. R&I give a different reading and translate the expression as : 'who like Rāma was endowed with several praiseworthy virtues'.
35. R&I translate vimala-svabhāvaḥ as 'who was very powerful'.
36. On kulajā Lakṣmī and vijaya-śrī, see Discussion and Analysis.
37. R&I fail to read some of the words in this verse correctly which has affected their translation also.
38. Other scholars have read the word as 'Indradhāma' and translated it accordingly. While 'ndu' and 'ndra' would not look much different in appearance from one another, the context decides our option in favour of 'indu' rather than 'Indra'. As for R&I's complaint that the author of the praśasti has failed to mention how the fame of Vajraṭa (wrongly quoted for Vajradeva) 'acted on the lotus-like faces of the damsels of the impenetrable enemy kings as he had described in the case of the virtuous people and the damsels of the quarters' (op. cit., p. 7) has no real basis as our translation would show.
39. R&I read the word as 'Bhavyasy=aitāḥ' but leave it untranslated.
40. Kīrtti here stands for the meritorious act as recorded in the grant and not just the eulogy as R&I suggest.
41. R&I wrongly read the name of the engraver as māhāḍa.

Discussion and Analysis

1. E.g. Gopāla I (in the Bhagalpur c.p. of Nārāyaṇapāla onwards, V. 1) and Śūrapāla I (Mirzapur c.p. of Śūrapāla, V.I). Nonetheless, the epithets here

- would be applicable to any of the Pāla kings from Gopāla I to Mahendrapāla. In that case, the epithet No. 8 would have reference to the Solar origin (cf. 'vaṁṣe Mihirasya jātavan', Kamauli c.p. of Vaidyadeva, V. 2, E.I., Vol. II, p. 350), and for the epithet No. 6, the emended reading 'mahā-dāna priya' would be more appropriate.
2. Cf. Khalimpur c.p. of Dharmapāla, V. 4, Gauḍalekhamālā, pp. 12, 19 and Note*.
 3. Itihās, No. 33, p. 3. In fact the expression under reference may be likened to 'Harim tvaktvā virāgād=iva śrīmad-yauvana-rūpa-sadguṇa-triṣā devyā Śrīy=āśleṣitaḥ' - discarding Hari, out of disinterest, Śrī (i.e. Lakṣmī) embraced the illustrious one (i.e. Śūrapāla I), attracted by his youthful appearance and craving his startling qualities, Mirzapur c.p. of Śūrapāla I, V. 18.
 4. This is a close parallel to V. 3 of the Bhagalpur c.p. of Nārāyaṇapāla (Gauḍalekhamālā, p. 57, reproduced in the Bharat Kala Bhavan c.p. of Rājya-pāla (R. N. Mishra, Chhavi - 2, p. 224).
 5. Further light on the Pāla - Kanauj - Indrāyudha-Cakrāyudha developments is thrown by the three copper plates of Gopāla II, son of Śūrapāla, dated year 3 (on which an illustrated talk was given by Mr. Ryosuke Furuī of Japan at the Centre of Archaeological Studies in Eastern India=CASTEI) and year 4 (two inscriptions, which have been unsatisfactorily edited by S.C. Mukherji in Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8, pp. 71-80, and which are expected to be re-edited by the present author soon. Many of the genealogical verses giving information about the early Pāla rulers are common in all the three inscriptions. The c.p. dated year 3 is now under the custody of the Archaeological Department of Bangladesh. Mr. Furuī took photographs of the c.p. and is expected to edit it soon. When published, it will make a significant addition to the storehouse of Pāla inscriptions.
 6. Gouriswar Bhattacharya, The Myth of Vikramādevī - Mother of Devapāla, Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8 (1997-1999), pp. 84-87.
 7. Cf. K. V. Ramesh and S. Subramoniya Iyer, Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XLII, pp. 8 and 25; Kamala Kanta Gupta, Itihās, Vol. 33, p. 3. One scholar has construed that the name of the queen of Dharmapāla was Nīti, Ashok Chattopadhyay Shastri, Pāl Abhilekh Sangraha, p. 118. S. C. Mukherji is in some hesitation about what to do with Vikramā vis a vis Raṇṇādevī, vide his Translation (in Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8, p. 66) of Verse 6 : 'he (the king) begot a son named Devapāla (or he begot by his beloved wife Vikramā an abode of morality, a son, named Devapāla?)'. Cf. also ibid., p. 59, where he writes: 'May it be conjectured that Vikramā was another name of Raṇṇā? But, methinks Messrs. Ramesh and Iyer have misinterpreted the passage ignoring the literal or real meaning.'
 8. Gouriswar Bhattacharya, op. cit., p. 85.
 9. The Mirzapur Plate of Śūrapāla also refers to the building by Devapāla of a temple (monastery) of Jina (=Buddha), that was golden (made of gold.

- jātarūpamayam=āyatanam Jinasya) the pinnacle of which was the most outstanding in the region of Jambunada (i.e. India ? Jambunad=ādi-śikhara-pratipakṣa-Lakṣmī), D.C. Sircar, Lucknow Museum (Discovered in the Mirzapur district of U.P.) Copper-Plate Inscription of Śūrapāla I, Regnal year 3, E.I., Vol. XL, pp. 7 and 12 (V. 12). The location of this temple is also unknown.
10. Cf. also the mention of Kedāra (Kedarnath in modern Uttarakhand) and Gokarna (in Nepal) in the Nalanda and Munger c.p.s (V.7) of Devapāla in connection with Dharmapāla's expeditions.
 11. It may be mentioned in this connection that according to the Bhagalpur c.p. (V. 6), copied in the Bharat Kala Bhavan c.p. of Rājyapāla, the king of Prāgyjyotiṣa (=Kāmarūpa, Assam) desisted from war-like preparations by accepting the order of Jayapāla (rājā Prāgyjyotiṣāṇām=upśamita-samit-samkathām yasya c=ājñām), son of Vākpāla, who acted on Devapāla's behalf during the latter's reign.
 12. K. V. Ramesh and S. Subramoniya Iyer, E. I., Vol. XLII, pp. 9-10.
 13. It is said in the c.p. inscriptions of Gopāla II that (his father) Śūrapāla had married Māṇikyadevī, granddaughter (dauhitrī) of the Cāhamāna king (Caman=ādhipasya) and daughter of king Rāmanvaka or Rāmandhaka (nripate Rāmandhakasy=ātmajāt=āsy=āsīd=Gaṇa vacchalasya mahiṣi Māṇikyadev=īti yā- V.6)
 14. Vide D. C. Sircar, Indian Epigraphy, Reprint, 1996, pp. 28 and 351; Pāl-Sen-Yuger Vamśānucarit, 1982, p. 63.
 15. See under Bibliography.
 16. For the most upto date list of the stone inscriptions of Mahendrapāla from north Bengal and Bihar, see Gouriswar Bhattacharya, Newly Discovered Copper Plate Grants of the Pāla Dynasty, p. 443.
 17. Formerly known as Gopāla II. Cf. Pramatha Nath Misra and R. C. Majumdar, The Jājilpārā Grant of Gopāla II, year 6, Journal of the Asiatic Society (of Bengal), Letters, Vol. XVII, No. 2, 1951, pp. 137-154.
 18. E. I. XLII, pp. 17 and 18 and notes 1 and 2 (p. 18). Ramesh and Iyer seem to have confused pārā (or pādā, the segment of a village) with pāra (or pāḍa, the bank of a tank/pond or river, ibid., p. 18, note 1.
 19. Ibid, pp. 17, 18, 21, 26 and 27.
 20. See K. V. Ramesh and S. Subramoniya Iyer, E. I. XLII; S. C. Mukherji, Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8; Kamala Kanta Gupta, Itihās, Vol. 33; Ashok Chattopadhyay Shastri, Pāl-Abhilekh Saṅgraha; B. N. Mukherjee, Purabhilekha Patrika, Journal of the Epigraphic Society of India, Vol. 23, 1997 under Bibliography.
 21. Gouriswar Bhattacharya, A Note against A Note on the Jagjibanpur Inscription of Mahendrapāla, Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8, p. 88.
 22. B. N. Mukherjee, An Inscribed Object from Jagjibanpur, ibid., p. 82.
 23. B. N. Mukherjee, A Note on the Jagjibanpur Inscription of Mahendrapāla, Purabhilekha Patrika, Vol. 23, p. 22.

24. See our Check Lists.
25. S. C. Mukherjee, The Jagajibanpur Copper-Plate Inscription of king Mahendrapāla, Regnal Year 7 (854 A. D.), The Maha-Bodhi Centenary Volume, Calcutta, pp. 173-176.
26. E.I., Vol. XLII, pp. 16-17.
27. Hirananda Shastri, The Nalanda Copper-Plate Inscription of Devapāladeva, E.I., Vol. XVII, pp. 322 and 325; N. G. Majumdar, Nalanda Copper-Plate of Devapāladeva, Monograph of the Varendra Research Society, Rajshahi, 1926, p. 23 and note 11, and p. 29.
28. E. I., Vol. XLII, p. 16.
29. Purabhilekha Patrika, Vol. 23, p. 22 and Notes 4 and 5.
30. See Note 27 above and also Bibliography.
31. See Note 27 above for reference, p. 325.
32. See Note 27 above for reference, p. 29.
33. Op. cit., p. 15.
34. Purabhilekha Patrika, Vol. 23, p. 22.
35. E. Hultzsch, The Bhagalpur Plate of Nārāyaṇapāla, The Indian Antiquary, 1886, pp. 304-310; Akshay Kumar Maitreya, Gauḍalekhamālā, reprint, Kolkata, 2004, pp. 55-69.
36. D. C. Bhattacharya, Indian Historical Quarterly, Vol. VI, pp. 53ff.; D. C. Sircar, Select Inscriptions, Vol. I, pp. 310-345.
37. Chiders, Dictionary of the Pali Language.
38. B. N. Mukherjee, Purabhilekha Patrika, Vol. 23, p. 23.
39. Ibid.
40. Cf. K. V. Ramesh and S. Subramoniya Iyer, E. I., Vol. XLII, p. 8.
41. Cf. D. C. Sircar, Pāl-Sen Yuger Vamśānucarit, Calcutta, 1982, p. 64. The observation made with reference to the grant of land in the Khalimpur c.p. of Dharmapāla, holds true with the present grant also.
42. D. C. Sircar, Lucknow Museum Copper-Plate Inscription of Śūrapāla, E.I., Vol. XL, pp. 4-16.
43. E.g. the Khalimpur c.p. of Dharmapāla and the Nalanda c.p. of Devapāla. The Murshidabad c.p. of Dharmapāla and the c.p. of Gopāla II, year 3 (both of which are as yet unpublished, but of which it has been possible to know the major content), seem to support this supposition.
44. K. V. Ramesh and S. Subramoniya Iyer, E. I., Vol. XLII, p. 15.
45. Kamala Kanta Gupta, Itihās, Vol. 33, pp. 3 and 4.
46. Cf. 'who have been conveyed (the royal order) self the (royal) messenger (dūtaka) from Mahāsenāpati Vajradeva', Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8, p. 68.
47. B. N. Mukherjee, ibid., p. 81 : 'In this record the king claimed to have been notified through the messenger (dūtaka) Mahāsenāpati Vajradeva'.
48. The choice of the expression 'Kamalā-nivāsaḥ' has been determined by his name (Nārāyaṇa).

49. The fact that these claims have been made in a Pāla c.p. grant (supposed to be prepared under royal order and official supervision with the royal (dynastic) seal bearing the king's name, cannot but be regarded as somewhat unusual. It would appear that in such cases where big institutional donations were made by high dignitaries outside the royal family, these dignitaries were given a free hand in introducing the eulogy of their own families. Vide Note 43 above for a few other examples.
50. Khalimpur c.p. of Dharmapāla, V. 13: 'yasy=ākarnṇayatas=trapā-vivalit=ānamraṁ sad=aiv=ānanarṁ'.
51. Cf. Nalanda and Munger c.ps of Devapāla, V. 10: 'Dhṛita-tanur=iyam Lakṣmīh sāksāt=kṣitir=nu śarīriṇī kim=avanipateḥ kīrttir=mūrtā 'thavā gṛih-adevatā iti vidadhatī śucy=ācārā vitarkavatīḥ prajāḥ.....'
52. The engraving of an inscription by a man of status is not altogether unknown. A close example is provided by the Mirzapur c.p. of Śūrapāla I which was engraved by Dakkadāsa and Vairocanadāsa, vide D.C. Sircar, E.I., Vol. XL, pp. 10 and 16; vide also Gouriswar Bhattacharya, Bangladesh National Museum Praśasti of Pāhila, Prācyaśikṣāsuhāsinī, p. 390.

Bibliography

- Barnett, L.D. - The Mongir Plate of Devapāladeva, E.I., Vol. XVIII, pp. 204ff. and plates.
- Batabyal, Umesh Chandra - The Khalimpur Copper-Plate of Dharmapāla, Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal, Vol. LXIII, Part I, pp. 39ff. and plates.
- ✓ Bhattacharya, Amitabha - A Note on King Mahendrapāla of the Jagjibanpur Copper Plate Inscription, Journal of the Asiatic Society (of Bengal), Vol. XXIX, No. 4, 1987, pp. 102-03; *ibid.*, Monthly Bulletin, 1-4 (1989, pp. 1-3.
- ✓ Do. - A Note on the Inscriptions Discovered in West Bengal between 1970-90, Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 1, 1992, pp. 161-64.
- Bhattacharya, D.C.-The Gunaighar Copper-Plate of Vainyagupta, Gupta Era 18, Indian Historical Quarterly (IHQ.), pp. 53ff. and plate (indistinct).
- Bhattacharya, Gouriswar (GB)- Newly Discovered copper Plate Grants of the Pāla Dynasty, Essays on Buddhist, Hindu and Jain Iconography, Studies in Bengal Art, Series No. 1, pp. 441-54.
- Do. - The New Pāla Ruler Mahendrapāla, Pratna Samiksha, Journal of the Directorate of Archaeology and Museums, Govt. of West Bengal, Vol. 1, 1992, pp. 165-70.
- Do. - The Myth of Vikramādevī - Mother of Devapāla? Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8 (1997-99), Kolkata, 2001, pp. 84-87.
- ✓ Do. - A Note against "A Note on the Jagjibanpur Inscription of Mahendrapāla", *ibid.*, pp. 88-90.
- Biswas Dilip Kumar, and Bhattacharya, Amitabha (ed.) - Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay Racaṇāvalī, 4th Volume (Complete Works of R. D. Banerji), published by

- Pascim Banga Rājya Pustak Parshat (West Bengal State Book Board), Calcutta, 1993. It refers to the Jagjibanpur and a few other newly discovered c. ps of West Bengal, pp. 50-51.
- Chattoadhyay Shastri, Ashok (ACS) - Pāl Abhilekh Sangraha (in Bengali), Paschim Banga Rājya Pustak Parshat (West Bengal State Book Board), Calcutta, 1992. The texts of the inscriptions are adapted from published works by other scholars without checking of the original inscriptions as a result of which these are not very reliable.
- Childers - Dictionary of the Pāli Language.
- Gaudalekhamālā - See under Maitreya, Akshay Kumar.
- Gupta, Kamala Kanta (KKG) - Article on the Jagjibanpur Copper-Plate Inscription of Mahendrapāla (with text and translation) reportedly published in the Darshak Patrikā (a Bengali Monthly periodical) in 1989, reports S. C. Mukherji (Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8, p. 58). We have not been able to see this article.
- ✓ Do. - Pāl-varṁśīya Caturtha Nṛipati Mahārājādnirāj Mahendrapāler Jagjibanpur Tāmraśāsan (Khrīṣṭīya navam śatābdī), Itihās (Bengali), 33rd Year, 1396 (b. S.) =1998, pp. 1-6.
- ✓ Do. - Navāviṣṭīya Jagjibanpur Tāmraśāsan (navam śatābdī), Pūrvādri (Bengali), Year 12, No. 3, August, 1991.
- Hultzsch, E. - The Bhagalpur Plate of Nārāyaṇapāla, The Indian Antiquary, 1886, pp. 304-10 and plates.
- Kielhorn, F. - Khalimpur Plate of Dharmapāladeva, E. I., VI. IV, pp. 243-54 and plate only of the seal.
- Do. - The Mongir Copper-Plate Grant of Devapāladeva, The Indian Antiquary, 1892, pp. 253-58 (no plate).
- ✓ Maitreya, Akshay Kumar - Gaudalekhamālā, published by the Varendra Research Society, Rajshahi, 1319 (B.S.); reprinted, Kolkata, 2004.
- Majumdar, Nani Gopal (NGM) - Nālandā Copper-Plate of Devapāladeva, Monograph (No. 1) of the Varendra Research Society, Rajshahi, 1926, pp. 1-31.
- Misra, Pramatha Nath and Majumdar, R. C. - The Jājilpārā Grant of Gopāla II (now Gopāla III), Year 6, Journal of the Asiatic Society (of Bengal), Letters, Vol. XVII, 1951, pp. 137-44 and plates.
- Misra, R. S. - Bharat Kala Bhavan (Banaras Hindu University) Copper-Plate Grant of Rājyapāla, Chhavi-2, Rai Krishnadasa Felicitation Volume, 1981, pp. 221-230 and plates. This c.p. has escaped the attention of D. C. Sircar.
- ✓ Mukherjee, B. N. (BNM) - A Note on the Jagjibanpur Inscription of Mahendrapāla, Purābhilekha Patrikā (Journal of the Epigraphic Society of India), Vol. 23, 1997, pp. 22-24.
- Do. - An Inscribed Object from Jagjibanpur, Pratna Samiksha, Vol. 6-8, 1997-99, Kolkata, 2002, pp. 81-83.
- Mukherji, Ramaranjan and Maity, Sachindra Kumar - Corpus of Bengal Inscriptions, Calcutta, 1967. The authors have apparently taken the texts from published

transcripts of other scholars without checking the readings of the original inscriptions, which compromises its reliability.

Mukherji, S. C. (SCM) - The three recently discovered copper plates of the Pāla Period, *Pratna Samiksha*, Vol. 1, pp. 171-74.

✓ Do. Pāla-nṛpateḥ Mahendrapālasya Jagajjībanapura-prāptam Tāmraśāsanam, *Sanskṛita Sāhitya Parishat Patrikā*, vol. LXVII, Nos. 1-12, April 1984 to March 1985 (1384 B. S.) pp. 201-04.

1987 ✓ Do. The Jagajjībanpur Copper-plate Inscription of King Mahendrapāla, Regnal Year 7 (854 A.D.?) *The Maha-Bodhi Centenary Volume*, Calcutta, pp. 173-76.

Do. The Jagajjībanpur Copper-Plate Inscription of King Mahendrapāla (of the Pāla Dynasty), regnal year 7 (857 A.D.), *Pratna Samiksha*, vol. 6-8 (1997-99), Kolkata, 2001, pp. 58-70.

Ramesh, K. V., and Iyer, S. Subramoniya (R&I) - Māldā District Museum Copper-Plate Charter of Mahendrapāladeva, Year 7, E. I., Vol. XLII, pp. 6-29 and plates.

Shastri, Hirananda - The Nalanda Copper-Plate Inscription of Devapāladeva, E.I., Vol. XVII, pp. 310-27 and plates.

Sircar, D. C. (DCS) - Gunaighar Copper Plate of Vainyagupta, Gupta Year 188, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, 2nd ed. (revised and enlarged), 1965, pp. 340-45.

✓ Do. - Khalimpur Copper-Plate of Dharmapāla, Regnal Year 32, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. II, Delhi, 1981, pp. 63 ff.

Do. - Nalanda Copper-Plate of Devapāla, Regnal Year 35, *ibid.*, pp. 71 ff.

Do. - Bhagalpur Copper-Plate of Nārāyaṇapāla, Regnal Year 17, *ibid.*, pp. 80 ff.

Do. - Lucknow Museum Copper-Plate Inscription of Śūrapāla I, Regnal Year 3, E. I., vol. XL, pp. 4-16 and plates.

Do. - *Indian Epigraphy*, Delhi, 1965; reprint, 1966.

Do. - *Indian Epigraphical Glossary*, Delhi, 1966.

Do. - *Pāl-Sen Yuger Vamśānucarit* (Bengali), Calcutta, 1982.

Do. - *Śilālekha - Tāmraśāsanādir Prasāṅga*, Calcutta, 1982

Venis, Arthur - Copper-Plate Grant of Vaidyadeva, king of Kāmarūpa, E. I., Vol. II, pp. 347-58 and plates.

West Bengal-An Archaeological Profile, Published by the Directorate of Archaeology & Museums, Informaiton & Cultural Affairs Department, Govt. of West Bengal, back cover page (sealing of the ārya-Bhikṣu- saṅgha of the monastery of Nandadīrghikā caused to be constructed by Śrī-Vajradeva).

Williams, M. Monier - *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*.

क
श
ल

JAGJIBANPUR COPPER-PLATE INSCRIPTION

A PALAEOGRAPHICAL CHART

Column 1 Initial vowels and consonants	Column 2 Consonants, medial vowels and Conjuncts						Column 3 Miscellaneous				
	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	i	ii	iii	iv	
A	अ						La	ल	ल	ल	
Ā	आ						Ṣa	भ			ava- graha
I	इ	ः	०	०			Ṣa	ष			
U	उ						Ṣa	य			anusvāra/ visarga
E	ए						Ra	र			
Ka	क						Conjuncts and medial vowels				यं णः लः यं yam lah yah
Kha	ख	श	ख	शु	khu		क्ष	ख	ल	ख	virāma =t
Ga	ग						hā	jā	ṭā	tā	
Gha	घ						ghā	jā	ṭā	tā	ophā
Ca	च						ca	chā	ṭā	tā	=n
Ja	ज	ञ	ज	ञ			ja	ja	ṭā	tā	=n
Ta	ट	ठ	ड	ड			ta	ta	ṭā	tā	=m
Da	ड	ड	ड	ड			da	da	ṭā	tā	=m
Na	ण	ण	ण	ण			na	na	ṭā	tā	
Ta	त						ta	ta	ṭā	tā	numer- als
Tha	थ	थ	थ	थ			tha	tha	ṭā	tā	
Da	द		thā	tho			da	da	ṭā	tā	auspicious symbol
Dha	ध						dha	dha	ṭā	tā	
Na	न						na	na	ṭā	tā	punctuation marks
Pa	प						pa	pa	ṭā	tā	
Pha	फ						pha	pha	ṭā	tā	
Ba-Va	व						ba	ba	ṭā	tā	Conjuncts
Bha	भ						bha	bha	ṭā	tā	jja ngam rtham
Ma	म						ma	ma	ṭā	tā	
Ya	य						ya	ya	ṭā	tā	
Ra	र						ra	ra	ṭā	tā	

Journal of Ancient Indian History

Rajesh Ranjan
15/5/09

Volume XXIII

2005-2006

Dineschandra Sircar Memorial Volume

Edited by

Subid Chattopadhyay

Head of the Department

Ancient Indian History and Culture

Calcutta University

CALCUTTA UNIVERSITY

1, Reformatory Street

Alipur, Kolkata 700 027

2007